

HyDelta 4

WP2 – Optimal grid concept at 16 bar

D2d.1 – Maintenance, operation and gas quality monitoring at 16 bar distribution grids

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Summary

As part of the national research programme HyDelta, a study was conducted into the potential additional maintenance and operation activities of a 16-bar hydrogen distribution grid compared to an 8-bar hydrogen distribution grid and an 8-bar natural gas distribution grid. The study focused on nine topics.

A large proportion of the activities related to maintenance, operation, and gas quality monitoring will change during the transition from 8 bar natural gas distribution grids to 8 bar hydrogen distribution grids. Changes or additions apply to six of the nine topics assessed. The difference between maintenance, operation, and gas quality monitoring for 8 bar versus 16 bar hydrogen distribution grids is more limited (see Table 1). At the higher pressure, the Dutch General Safety Instructions (VI-Hydrogen) and the underlying Safety Work Instructions (VWI's) will need to be adapted. Additionally, in the event of a leak in a 16 bar hydrogen distribution grid, leakage will be greater due to the higher pressure difference across the leak opening. This leads to wider safety distances. Equipment and measuring instruments suitable for the use in 8 bar distribution grids may not be suitable for a pressure of 16 bar. This may therefore result in the purchase of new equipment.

Safety instructions

In this study, it was determined that the Dutch Hydrogen Safety Instructions need to be amended for applications up to a pressure of 16 bar. This is primarily due to the need to evaluate several risks and associated safety measures.

Digitalization

For both 8 bar and 16 bar hydrogen grids, digitalization has added value, as was also observed at HyDelta 2 WP8 [1] [2]. Digitalization offers solutions where other measures are not possible or are ineffective. For 16 bar hydrogen grids, there are no additional or different aspects related to digitalization that change compared to 8 bar hydrogen grids.

Cathodic protection

For a cathodic protection system (CP system), virtually nothing additional is required when operating an 8 bar or 16 bar hydrogen distribution grid compared to an 8 bar natural gas grid. Different procedures may be necessary only at locations where sparks and gas leaks can occur.

Emissions

In 8 bar and 16 bar hydrogen distribution grids, CO₂ - equivalent emissions are lower than in 8 bar natural gas grids. For this reason, it is not necessary to apply a higher frequency of leak detection in a 16 bar hydrogen distribution grid.

Gas stations - general and ATEX inspections

It is recommended to inspect every type of hydrogen gas station (supplying from an 8 bar or 16 bar grid) at least annually. This represents an increase in the frequencies applied by regional grid operators at 8 bar natural gas stations.

The ATEX inspections at 8 bar or 16 bar hydrogen gas stations are expected to be carried out with the same frequency as the inspections at 8 bar natural gas stations. The focus points for these inspections are of the same design. However, differences may arise in content between the ATEX inspections at hydrogen stations and natural gas stations. This follows from the initial ATEX assessment.

Gas quality monitoring – general and by type of feeder

Due to the significant influence of contaminants on gas quality and the stricter requirements imposed on hydrogen compared to natural gas, hydrogen quality must be monitored more closely. Other parameters must be taken into account, and the limit values for those parameters are also different. A 16 bar hydrogen grid requires no additional monitoring beyond that of an 8 bar hydrogen grid.

With supply by the Dutch Hydrogen Network Services (HNS, top-down), hydrogen of a more consistent quality can be expected compared to other suppliers (bottom-up). The supply of hydrogen by HNS to the distribution companies can be monitored in the same way as is currently done in the Netherlands for the supply of natural gas by Gasunie. This methodology also does not need to change in the event of a pressure increase to 16 bar.

For the supply of hydrogen by smaller feeders (other than HNS), a methodology for monitoring gas quality can be applied as is currently done for biomethane feed-in. This entails;

- 1) Continuous monitoring by the gas supplier
- 2) Periodic check (e.g. once a month) on THT and olfactory testing by an external party
- 3) Periodic inspection (e.g. once every six months) of gas quality and inspection of the operation of the gas chromatograph by an external party.

Additional conditions and risks

Before a hydrogen distribution grid is operated at 16 bar, several basic conditions must be met (see 10.1). In addition, risks may increase. To keep or reduce the risks during maintenance and operation to an acceptable level, measuring instruments and equipment must be able to withstand a pressure of 16 bar. Measures to reduce the **likelihood** of hazards occurring when operating a 16 bar distribution grid, as well as to reduce the potential **effects** of those hazards, are largely the same as the measures applied when operating an 8 bar hydrogen distribution grid. In most cases, larger safety distances are required for a 16 bar grid (see 10.4), because leakage rates may be higher. The suitability of measuring instruments and equipment will need to be determined in further detail.

In Table 1 on the following page, the changes mentioned above are presented in a single overview.

Table 1 The transition from 8 bar hydrogen distribution grids to 16 bar hydrogen distribution grids has a limited impact on maintenance and operation activities.

Subject	Will maintenance, operation, and gas quality monitoring be different for 16 bar hydrogen grids compared to ...		Further explanation in chapter
	8 bar natural gas	8 bar hydrogen	
Safety (work) instructions	yes	yes	2
Digitalization	yes	no	3
Cathodic protection	possible	no	4
Frequency maintenance and leak detection related to emissions	no	no	5
Gas station inspection policy	yes	no	6
ATEX inspections (gas stations)	yes	no	7
Gas quality monitoring - general	yes	no	8
Gas quality monitoring dependent on importers	no	no	9
Additional conditions/risks	yes	yes	10

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1. Background and objective

1.1 General

This research was conducted within the framework of the national research programme HyDelta. This programme focuses on the safe integration of hydrogen into the existing infrastructure for gas transport and distribution. Its objective is to remove barriers for innovative hydrogen projects. The entire research programme is divided into work packages. For an explanation of the various work packages, see www.hydelta.nl

This report concerns the maintenance and operation of hydrogen distribution grids up to and including 16 bar.

1.2 Problem statement and background

The current natural gas distribution grids are built with a Maximum Operating Pressure (MOP) of 8 bar. During the initial construction of hydrogen grids in industrial environments, grid operators are asked to operate the grids at 16 bar. Consequently, the question from regional gas grid operators is what additional requirements are needed for the maintenance and operation of a 16-bar hydrogen distribution grid compared to an 8-bar hydrogen grid and an 8-bar natural gas distribution grid.

1.3 Objective

The aim of this research is to answer the following research questions:

1. What needs to be adjusted in the content of the VIAG and VWI's (Dutch Safety Instructions) ?
2. What is the added value of digitalization?
3. What about cathodic protection and hydrogen?
4. What additional conditions/risks are involved in operating 16 bar hydrogen gas grids?
5. What is the effect on emissions, and should the frequency of maintenance and leak detection be increased?
6. What inspection policy is necessary for gas stations?
7. Does the gas quality of hydrogen need to be monitored additionally?
8. Is there a difference in gas quality when fed in by Hydrogen Network Services and other gas suppliers?
9. How should ATEX regulations be handled?

Answering these questions provides insight into the need for additional measures for the operation of 16 bar hydrogen gas grids.

Each of the above-mentioned questions is discussed in a separate chapter.

2. Does the content of the Safety Work Instructions need to be adjusted?

An important part of the safety policy for the maintenance and operation of the natural gas grid in The Netherlands is laid down in the VIAG (“VeiligheidsInstructies Aardgas”; Safety Instructions Natural Gas) and the associated VWI’s (“Veiligheids WerkInstructies”; Safety Work Instructions). Such a system is also desirable when working on hydrogen distribution grids.

At the start of this investigation, it became clear that Safety Instructions Hydrogen (“VI-Waterstof”) had already been drawn up by the Dutch Distribution System Operators (DSO’s). These instructions have a similar structure to the Safety Instructions Natural Gas (“VIAG”) and applicable to distribution grids up to 8 bar. Additionally, at the start of this study, concept Safety Work Instructions (VWI’s) for hydrogen had been drawn up by the DSO’s, likewise for a pressure of up to 8 bar.

In this study, it was determined that both the Safety Instructions Hydrogen and the Safety Work Instructions must be amended for applications up to a pressure of 16 bar. This is primarily due to the need to evaluate several risks and associated safety measures. This is explained in more detail in the following paragraphs.

2.1 What is the VIAG?

The “VIAG” and the associated “VWI’s” together form a uniform set of rules for safe operation in gas systems of Dutch DSO’s. Both grid operators and contractors working in these systems must follow these rules. Because the organization of each grid operator may differ, not all details are regulated in the VIAG; each grid operator records deviating or additional matters in its own operational procedures, to which the VIAG refers where necessary.

The VIAG and the associated work instructions are updated annually and fulfill the requirements of the Dutch law (“Arbowet” and “Arbobesluit”) related to working conditions for work on gas supply systems. Netbeheer Nederland (GVR, a Dutch Group dealing with Safety Regulations) establishes and manages these instructions.

The VIAG was originally drafted for natural gas grids with an operating pressure of up to 8 bar. The installation managers of the Dutch gas grid operators have since conducted a Risk Inventory and Evaluation (RI&E) and developed adjustments based on it to create a similar policy document for hydrogen gas grids, the “VI-Hydrogen”.

The draft version of this new hydrogen document has been shared with KIWA as part of the project. The document focuses on hydrogen grids with an operating pressure of up to and including 8 bar. Section 2.4 identifies risks that may change with a pressure increase to 16 bar. If these risks change, the measures may also need to be adjusted.

2.2 Differences in structure of workpermits

A workpermit is a written document in which specific powers and responsibilities are assigned for the management and operation of a gas supply system. The designation system from the VIAG has been compared with that of the VI-Hydrogen. This comparison shows that there are no differences between the two systems.

It should be noted, however, that the current draft version of the “VI-Hydrogen” is only valid for installations with an operating pressure of up to 8 bar. The Risk Inventory and Evaluation (RI&E) may indicate that an additional instruction is required when a grid is operated at 16 bar. However, this RI&E has yet to be carried out.

2.3 Draft VWI's Hydrogen

In the submitted draft Safety Work Instructions for hydrogen, the relevant risks were identified and described based on a system pressure of 8 bar. This study investigated which risks change when the operating pressure is increased to 16 bar. Based on this assessment, it was determined whether an evaluation of the control measures is necessary to ensure safe operation under the elevated pressure conditions.

The Safety Work Instructions as mentioned in Table 2 have been declared applicable by the current VIAG working group for hydrogen distribution grids up to 8 bar.

Table 2: List of valid VWI's (as provided as a working document)

Number	Description
G-01	Identify pipelines to safely carry out gas-related work
H ₂ -06	Safely install, replace, or remove hydrogen meters ≤ G25
H ₂ -07	Safely test indoor installations and meter setups ≤ G25 for leak tightness.
H ₂ -08	Safely fill indoor installations ≤ G25 with hydrogen
H ₂ -09	Safely install, replace, or remove hydrogen meters HP or > G25 LP
H ₂ -10	LP hydrogen meter installations ≤ G25 including main shut-off valves, safe repair and maintenance
H ₂ -11	Safely connect and commission new LP hydrogen service lines and meter installations
H ₂ -12	Safely test LP hydrogen service lines for strength and tightness
H ₂ -13	Safely filling LP hydrogen service lines with hydrogen
H ₂ -14	Safe working on existing LP hydrogen service lines and meter installations, excluding the main shut-off valve.
H ₂ -15	Safely installing and commissioning HP connection cables
H ₂ -17	Working safely on gas saddles and pressurized branching points in LP grids (without gas leakage)
H ₂ -20	Safely commissioning and decommissioning LP pipelines
H ₂ -21	Safely commission and decommission HP pipelines and/or shut them down
G-22	Safely test the strength of HP and LP cables and HP connection cables
G-23	Safely test HP and LP pipes and HP connection pipes for leaks
H ₂ -24	Safely installing and removing gas bladders in LP lines
G-25	Safely stopple HP pipes
G-27	Safely clamping PE pipes and PE and PVC connection pipes in existing HP and LP grids

G-28	(Branch=deleted) Safely weld and tap fittings onto PE in existing HP and LP grids
G-29	Safely welding and tapping fittings onto steel in existing HP and LP pipelines
G-31	Safely inspecting the lining of HP and LP pipes
G-35	Safe above-ground gas leak detection
H ₂ -36	Securing the area around and safely locating gas leaks
H ₂ -37	Safely repairing leaks in HP and LP pipelines
G-41	Safely taking gas samples in HP and LP grids
G-42	Safely operating ground shut-off valves in HP and LP grids and connection lines
G-43	Safely inspecting ground shut-off valves and fittings in HP and LP grids
G-45	Safely perform CP measurements
G-46	Safely installing test leads for cathodic protection on gas-carrying pipelines
G-47	Working safely with natural gas condensate
G-50	Safely performing non-gas-related work in gas-related business premises
H ₂ -51	Safely perform functional inspections on hydrogen technical installations and metering setups > G25
H ₂ -52	Safely performing gas-related work in hydrogen technology facilities
G-53	Safely perform work on EVHIs
H ₂ -54	commissioning and decommissioning hydrogen pressure regulating and metering stations
HP = High Pressure = > 100 mbar LP = Low Pressure = < 100 mbar	

2.4 Risks as stated in the VWIs and the VI-Hydrogen

In the Safety Work Instructions described in Table 2, various risks have been identified that have been assessed as manageable at a system pressure of 8 bar, with corresponding measures. However, these risks may increase with an increase in pressure to 16 bar. Table 3 lists all those risks appearing in the Safety Work Instructions or the Hydrogen Safety Instructions that may change due to the pressure increase from 8 to 16 bar.

Table 3: Overview of identified risks for which measures must be evaluated for effectiveness

Risk
Presence of people and/or animals in the immediate vicinity of the workplace or the outlet opening of the vent of flare unit.
Uncontrolled outflow of hydrogen.
Invisible hydrogen flame, e.g. at the flare unit or unexpected ignition
Risk of explosion in case of excessive hydrogen concentration during venting
Due to the low ignition energy, there is a risk of fire and/or explosion when venting larger quantities (> 100 liters) of hydrogen.
Hearing damage caused by escaping or burning hydrogen.
Fire and/or explosion hazard.
Personal injury due to burns.
<i>Related to the high pressure grid, over one hundred risks have been identified in the VWIs as listed in Table 1. These include risks with more or less the same nature. Of these more than one hundred risks, eight risks may change with a pressure increase from 8 to 16 bar.</i>

When the pressure is increased to 16 bar, the existing measures associated with the risks as listed in Table 3be reassessed to determine whether they remain adequate under the new pressure conditions. The pressure increase may affect both the probability and the severity of the identified risks. The current measures can only be considered sufficient if it can be demonstrated that the risks remain within the acceptance criteria even at the higher pressure. If this is not the case, additional technical or organizational measures must be considered.

Based on the evaluation carried out, the VWIs and the VI-Hydrogen will need to be adjusted.

3. What is the added value of digitalization?

Digitalization¹ is increasingly being used for the monitoring and control of gas grid management. Digitalization can play an important role in implementing the necessary additional measures, but it also entails extra investments and costs for the management of the systems. Furthermore, the use of these types of capabilities impacts work processes and personnel responsibilities.

For both 8 bar and 16 bar hydrogen grids, digitalization has added value, as was also observed at HyDelta 2 WP8 [1] [2]. Digitalization offers solutions where other measures are not possible or are ineffective. For 16 bar hydrogen grids, there are no additional or different aspects related to digitalization that change compared to 8 bar hydrogen grids.

- **Facilitating balancing**
Monitoring and central regulations make it possible to facilitate the balancing of supply and demand.
- **Gas quality monitoring**
Monitoring of gas quality combined with the ability to shut off remotely helps to keep the quality within the agreed range.
- **Increasing safety.**
Sensors can help detect a problem earlier, and remotely controlled valves make it possible to intervene much faster.
- **More reliable computational models**
Sensors provide better insight into what is actually happening in the grid. As a result, computational models can also be validated and improved. Computational models are important, among other things, for properly assessing current and future situations.

The use of more digital technologies means a new type of work and changes in work processes and responsibilities for the staff.

- **New type of work for maintenance and operation**
Installing, maintaining, and troubleshooting sensors, signal cabinets, remotely controlled equipment, the monitoring portal, and the associated SCADA and telemetry systems is not a new field [1]. However, an expansion of use and an increase in importance will mean that more work needs to be done in this area and that new knowledge will also be required.
- **New work processes and responsibilities**
An increase in data necessitates a different approach to monitoring and intervention. Particularly if the intention is to intervene more quickly, this also entails new work processes and new responsibilities. This certainly applies if the grid operator is going to facilitate balancing. Note: facilitating does not necessarily mean an executive role for the grid operator, but at the very least that the grid operator must take the ongoing processes surrounding balancing into account in its work processes.

¹Digitization refers to: The application of digital techniques for monitoring, modeling, and control of the gas network [1]. This involves the use of telemetry to make sensor information accessible in real time and to control equipment remotely. The sensor information is combined with computational models to gain insight into the behavior of the network in the given situation.

3.1 What is the added value of digitalization?

Digitization presents both advantages and disadvantages. The advantages lie in better insight through more and faster access to up-to-date information, and opportunities for quicker intervention and the application of automation. The disadvantages concern the additional costs for installation and maintenance, and new risks introduced by digitization.

It is important to note that digital techniques are already being used in natural gas grids. Among other things, these types of techniques are already being deployed to monitor and facilitate feeding in by multiple parties (biomethane feeders). The extent to which the currently used techniques in natural gas grids are suitable for application in hydrogen grids varies by technique and application. Further analysis of this falls outside the scope of this research.

Benefits: more (up-to-date) information, faster intervention, new possibilities

Sensors provide insight into what is actually taking place in the grid. This is in contrast to information based solely on calculations (modeling). By combining current information with modeling, a good understanding of the grid's behavior can be obtained. The trend over time is also important in this regard, so it concerns not only current data but also historical data. Examples of current information that can be monitored by sensors include pressures, flow rates, and gas composition, as well as, for instance, the intervention of a safety device.

Electronically controlled components make it possible to intervene in the grid from a central location (control room). Examples include closing a valve, adjusting the pressure setting in a control circuit, or resetting a safety device. Regulating the flow rate is also possible. This saves time and potentially costs.

Based on current and historical information from sensors and the availability of remotely controllable equipment:

- **problems can be identified (earlier)**
For example, a sudden pressure drop combined with a large increase in flow rates may indicate a major leak. If, on the other hand, only the pressure drops, this may indicate that a safety mechanism has intervened. Because the location of the sensors is known, the problem can be localized based on this information by combining it with modeling. By equipping the monitoring with smart algorithms, problems can be detected even before the first alerts are received. Remotely controllable equipment also makes it possible to intervene more quickly.
- **problems can be prevented**
By closely monitoring and calibrating the history of sensors, it is also possible to detect changes. Based on this, it is possible to anticipate certain problems, allowing the issue to be prevented through timely intervention. The French company GRTgaz, for example, succeeded in detecting and correcting pressure control drift in stations in a timely manner using this method [3].
- **the operation of the gas grid can be optimized for, for example, injection**
For instance, if there are various inputs and/or buffers, insight into the actual flow rates and pressures occurs helps to better align the various control systems. Here too, it is important to combine the measured data with modeling so that the behavior of the grid can be accurately mapped. Remotely controllable equipment makes it possible to make immediate adjustments to the control systems upon detecting imbalance.
- **better predictions for supply and demand can be made by combining this with other data**
It is already possible to make predictions about energy demand based on profiles. By combining this knowledge with modeling and knowledge about the climate, it is possible to

predict how often supply and demand are out of balance (this is already possible in certain modeling software). By adding sensor data to this, the models become even more accurate.

The smart combination of information from sensors and remote control also opens up new possibilities. For example, in the field of automation and the application of artificial intelligence. Examples of this type of development can already be found, such as predicting excavation damage [4].

Disadvantages: higher investments, extra maintenance, and new risks

There are costs associated with the use of these types of capabilities. Firstly, these involve investment costs for adding sensors, remotely controllable equipment, and the associated telemetry system. The investment costs also include adapting existing software and developing new software that utilizes the information flows. Consider, for example, modifications to the software used for modeling [1] [2]. By intelligently combining modeling and sensor data, the number of required sensors and the associated costs can be kept to a minimum.

The additional costs do not only concern the investments. The sensors, equipment, and telemetry must also be maintained and may require repair.

Although the use of digitalization can actually help reduce the risks of malfunctions, it also introduces new risks itself. In any case, malfunctions of the equipment itself will have to be resolved. In addition, digitalization poses new risks to the proper functioning of the grid that would otherwise not exist. Suppose, for example, that a sensor transmits incorrect information without it being noticed that the sensor itself is the problem. This can lead to incorrect action. If, for instance, a sensor indicates excessively high pressure, an incorrect adjustment to the pressure control could be made based on this. The failure of electronically controlled components can directly cause malfunctions in the grid: for example, a valve closing incorrectly due to a problem with the electronics.

In addition, digitalization requires due attention to security, particularly regarding the IT side of the system, to prevent it from being hacked. At a minimum, this involves preventing the leakage of potentially sensitive data. Furthermore, where IT connects with operational technology (OT) for remotely electronically controlled components, it must be prevented that the grid can be disrupted via a hack.

Relevance for 16 bar hydrogen grids

The use of digitalization is relevant for both existing 8 bar natural gas grids and 8 bar and 16 bar hydrogen grids. In this regard, particularly for hydrogen grids, it is becoming increasingly relevant to have facilities to balance supply and demand, but this is also relevant for natural gas grids due to the increase in biomethane suppliers. Digitalization can be an important tool to enable balancing [1] [2], making optimal use of the permitted pressure variation. The balance can be monitored using pressure sensors and flow measurements. Subsequently, using remotely controllable equipment (controllers and valves), it is possible to better maintain the balance between supply and demand in accordance with contractual agreements.

Digitalization can help reduce risks. For example, remotely operated shut-off valves make it possible to shut off the gas much faster in the event of an emergency. This can significantly reduce the likelihood of escalation. This might be slightly more relevant for a 16 bar hydrogen grid, as the higher pressure entails a higher risk.

3.2 Are such measures necessary?

The necessity of digitalization depends on the requirements and preconditions imposed on the operation of the hydrogen grid. These requirements stem not only from contractual agreements, but also from the requirements in the Energy Act and requirements set by the regulator regarding, for example, gas quality. Digitalization primarily concerns requirements regarding:

- balancing supply and demand
- requirements regarding gas quality
- narrower bandwidths, e.g. for pressure

Digital techniques are an important tool for facilitating balancing. However, the question remains whether balancing facilities must be provided by the grid operator. Alternatively, a choice could be made for buffers or a connection to a national hydrogen transport grid, in which case consideration must also be given to feeding back excess capacity. In that case, buffering will presumably not be part of the distribution grid and will therefore fall outside the responsibility of the grid operator. This could mean that the need for digitalization regarding balancing is eliminated.

Another important reason for digitalization could be requirements regarding gas quality. For example, it is quite conceivable that continuous monitoring of gas quality will be required by the regulator. Additionally, higher requirements may be set for pressure bandwidths. Digitalization may be necessary for this as well, to monitor and regulate the pressure.

3.3 What kind of impact does this have on the staff?

The increased use of digitalization impacts work processes and the required knowledge and expertise. This particularly affects activities related to monitoring and control, maintenance, and malfunctions. Additionally, the availability of new (historical) data will be important for the various analyses used for policy formulation and prioritization. New analytical capabilities do not require new knowledge and skills from the personnel involved. This will apply especially to the first three points mentioned, as explained further below.

Monitoring and control

When monitoring the proper functioning of the grid, (many) additional data become available. Personnel must be trained to correctly interpret the data, their interrelationships, and their relationship with other data (such as current work in progress).

If remotely controllable components are present, this creates new tasks and responsibilities. Especially when it comes to services related to balancing and monitoring gas quality, this represents a completely new field of expertise. New protocols will also need to be developed and training required for this.

Maintenance

The maintenance of sensors and electronically operated components requires new knowledge and qualifications. Existing staff will need to learn how to use the new equipment. Additionally, specialized personnel may be required to maintain and repair the equipment. The task of keeping security up to standard is also important. Developments in security are moving fast. This requires constant vigilance to keep up with these developments and adapt accordingly.

Malfunctions

The availability of more information means new possibilities for fault analysis and problem prediction. Personnel will need to be trained to use this correctly. The availability of remotely controllable components will lead to adjusted procedures for approaching and resolving malfunctions, especially in situations where rapid action is required.

4. What about cathodic protection?

For a cathodic protection system (CP system), virtually nothing additional is required when operating an 8 bar or 16 bar hydrogen distribution grid compared to an 8 bar natural gas grid. Different procedures may be necessary only at locations where sparks and gas leaks can occur.

4.1 Other procedures may be necessary

Cathodic protection cannot cause sparks during normal operation. The electrical currents and voltages are far too low for this. Nevertheless, sparks can occur under certain circumstances, for example due to the induction of AC voltage from high-voltage systems, lightning strikes, or short circuits. This is particularly relevant for cathodic protection systems with impressed current. In this case, the critical locations are the rectifier and non-connected insulating joints (for electrical separation) situated in an area with a risk of flammable gas mixtures.

A rectifier is a device that converts alternating current into direct current to protect a pipeline against corrosion (see figure 1). Such a device contains various electrical circuits and components, such as a circuit breaker. Consequently, it must not be installed in a zone with a risk of flammable gases without a protective enclosure.

Figure 1. Two rectifiers: left with transformer, right with “switched-mode power supply”.

Non-connected insulating joints are used to electrically isolate the cathodically protected pipeline from installations such as pump or compressor stations, gas pressure regulating stations, and metering installations (see figure 2). These insulating joints are often located above ground. Insulating joints are also frequently incorporated in the protected pipeline itself. These are placed underground within the pipeline and are electrically connected to each other above ground (in a test station). In zones with a risk of flammable gases, “spark gaps” are often placed at the insulating joints to prevent sparking.

Figure 2. An above-ground insulating joint for electrical separation.

A spark can lead to dangerous situations involving flammable gas mixtures. Therefore, CP installations in areas prone to such gas mixtures must comply with standards for explosive atmospheres (ATEX, see Annex II). In these standards, natural gas falls under group IIA. Mixtures of natural gas with hydrogen gas can be categorized as group IIA, IIB, or IIC gas. 100% Hydrogen is a group IIC gas. A different category may have implications for the impressed current CP system in these types of areas. [5]

Possible adjustments to procedures for KB therefore depend primarily on the risk of a hazardous gas mixture. This risk may differ for a hydrogen pipeline compared to a natural gas pipeline, but also when using a higher gas pressure, such as 16 bar instead of 8 bar.

4.2 The operation of CP remains the same

There are various literature sources, such as ASME, EIGA, PRCI, Gasunie, and Marcogaz, stating that the operation of cathodic protection remains the same for steel hydrogen pipelines as for steel natural gas pipelines. This will also apply to hydrogen pipelines at 16 bar.

The American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) has a specific standard for hydrogen lines, namely ASME 31.12-2023 “*Hydrogen Piping and Pipelines*”. This standard describes the application of both industrial pipelines for gaseous and liquefied hydrogen, as well as general pipelines used for the transport of hydrogen gas. This standard also includes requirements for maintenance. Cathodic protection is mentioned in this section, as it is an essential component for keeping steel (hydrogen) pipelines in good condition. However, no specific requirements are set for the cathodic protection system. [6]

The European Industrial Gases Association (EIGA) also has a specific document on hydrogen pipelines, namely IGC Doc 121/14 “*Hydrogen Pipeline Systems*”. Here too, the importance of cathodic protection to prevent corrosion is emphasized. For the implementation of cathodic protection, reference is made to a general CP standard, namely EN 12954. No remarks, comments, or additional measures are required for the application of CP to hydrogen pipelines. [7]

Furthermore, the Pipeline Research Council International (PRCI) states that no changes are necessary to the application of cathodic protection with the introduction of hydrogen gas into a grid. [8]

In 2019, Gasunie drafted a document explaining why the cathodic protection (CP) system does not need to be adjusted if the medium is hydrogen gas instead of natural gas [5]. Gasunie states that hydrogen gas is a non-electrically conductive gas, meaning it cannot cause corrosion of the pipeline. As a result, there is no interaction between the hydrogen gas in the pipeline and the cathodic protection of the underground pipeline.

Finally, cathodic protection in transmission pipelines (>16 bar) for 100 vol% hydrogen gas is classified as “no significant problems in available studies” in an overview of available test results for hydrogen admission to Marcogaz’s existing natural gas infrastructure. [9]

4.3 The contribution of CP to hydrogen embrittlement cannot be ruled out

The hydrogen molecules (H_2) of hydrogen gas can break down into individual hydrogen atoms (H) at the steel surface. These hydrogen atoms can then penetrate the steel and, in certain types of steel, lead to hydrogen embrittlement at sufficiently high pressure and temperature. However, there is hardly any difference in the contribution of these hydrogen atoms between 8 bar and 16 bar hydrogen pipelines. In both cases, the influence is very low.

Hydrogen is also formed through cathodic protection. This can lead to detachment of the coating and, theoretically, to hydrogen embrittlement. However, this process is not unique to hydrogen pipelines, but applies to all pipelines that are cathodically protected. To date, the European Gas Pipeline Incident Data Group (EGIG) has not recorded any incidents resulting from hydrogen embrittlement. [5]

Nevertheless, it is currently unknown whether the coating will detach more easily if hydrogen is formed not only by the cathodic protection, but if the pipeline also transports hydrogen gas. The same applies to hydrogen embrittlement, where the combined contribution of cathodic protection and hydrogen transport is not yet fully known. [8, 10]

The procedures however do not need to be adjusted. The quality of the coating can be checked in the normal way using, for example, current density measurements or additional measurements such as DCVG or ACVG. The risk of hydrogen embrittlement in distribution pipelines is very low, so the normal procedures for CP are applied to hydrogen pipelines (see also the section 4.2 “The operation of CP remains the same”).

See the box on the next page for a general explanation of cathodic protection.

What is CP?

Underground steel objects and pipes are protected against rust by applying a coating. This can be, for example, a layer of paint, epoxy, or polyethylene (PE). In the past, bitumen was also widely used. Additionally, the object is “cathodically protected” (CP). This is therefore a technique to prevent corrosion.

In a simple method, the metal to be protected (for example, steel) is electrically connected to a less noble metal (for example, magnesium). As a result, the less noble metal will corrode and dissolve, while the other metal is protected. This is “cathodic protection with a sacrificial anode”.

The metal can also be bonded to a nobler metal (such as silicon iron). In that case, a current source (rectifier) is required to ensure that the noble metal dissolves and the other metal remains protected. This is called “cathodic protection with impressed current”.

Figure 3 Schematic principle of cathodic protection by impressed current, where in this case a current source (the rectifier) ensures that the pipeline is protected due to an incoming electrical current.

5. What is the effect on emissions, and should the frequency of maintenance/leak detection be increased?

In the operation of hydrogen installations, an increase in operating pressure from 8 to 16 bar can affect the occurrence and magnitude of leaks. Therefore, a key question is whether increasing the pressure leads to more or larger hydrogen emissions, and whether the current leak detection interval is still appropriate.

In 8 bar and 16 bar hydrogen distribution grids, CO₂ equivalent emissions are lower than in 8 bar natural gas grids. For this reason, it is not necessary to apply a higher frequency of leak detection in a 16 bar hydrogen distribution grid.

5.1 Methane and hydrogen as greenhouse gases

Emissions arise in a distribution grid at various locations and during diverse activities. Due to the impact on safety, the environment, and costs, these emissions are limited as much as possible. Methane is a strong greenhouse gas. Two-thirds of global methane emissions are caused by humans [11], and methane has accounted for approximately 30% of global warming since the Industrial Revolution [12].

Although hydrogen is not a direct greenhouse gas itself, it does contribute to climate change as an indirect greenhouse gas by slowing down the breakdown of methane and thereby potentially increasing the atmospheric concentration of powerful greenhouse gases.

5.2 Quantification of emissions via GWP

The potential of gases as greenhouse gases is expressed in Global Warming Potential (GWP). This is a number that indicates, for a specific time span, how many times stronger the greenhouse effect of a ton of the gas is compared to a ton of CO₂. Over a period of 100 years (GWP100), this is 30 for methane, and over a period of 20 years (GWP20), it is 82.5. This difference between these values arises because methane remains in the atmosphere for an average of only 12 years, but over that period, it retains much more heat than CO₂. An advantage of this, however, is that a reduction in the emission of this gas leads to a drop in the earth's temperature within a short period of time.

Hydrogen is an indirect greenhouse gas and has a GWP100 of 11.6 +/- 2.8 and a GWP20 of 37.3 +/- 15.1 [13]. An indirect greenhouse gas does not absorb heat itself, but in the atmosphere, through chemical reactions, it ensures that methane is broken down less rapidly and more ozone is formed; both of these substances absorb heat and retain it on Earth. The residence time of hydrogen in the atmosphere is approximately 2 years. [14]

Because various variables influence the total outflow of hydrogen from a grid, it is difficult to predict exactly how large the effect of hydrogen emissions on global warming will be. Variables that play a role in this include, for example, the type of leaks, the ratio of grid components, and the amount of hydrogen to be transported. According to current calculations, the Dutch natural gas grid loses less than 0.1% of the transported volume due to leaks. Production and end-use are not included in these figures. It is important to monitor this closely and to map out the expected leaks for hydrogen as well.

It is expected that hydrogen will eventually be subject to legislation similar to the European methane emission regulation. It is therefore advisable to start working on emission reduction measures for hydrogen in advance. These measures will largely be comparable to the reduction measures for methane emissions. A separate law will have to be drafted for hydrogen emissions, which could take years.

The current methane emission legislation consists of a number of components:

- Monitoring and reporting
- Leak Detection and Repair (LDAR)
- Venting and flaring

Flaring may not be discouraged, because hydrogen does not produce greenhouse gases (except water vapor, the emission of which has no impact on the climate [15]). For the time being, reusing hydrogen instead of flaring has the advantage that no valuable gas is lost.

The biggest difference between methane and hydrogen will be that detection methods will need to be adapted for hydrogen. Hydrogen has different absorption spectra than methane. For instance, it absorbs much less infrared light than methane. Adapted detection methods for hydrogen are already under development. [16]

5.3 Leak detection frequency

When there is an ambition to reduce hydrogen emissions, or when this becomes legally mandatory, increasing the frequency of leak detection is in many cases the most direct and simplest measure to reduce emissions. By converting natural gas to hydrogen and increasing the operating pressure to 16 bar, the flow rate of leaks will increase by a factor of 2.4 [17]. However, the equivalent CO₂ emission will decrease as calculated below.

An example calculation:

Methane GWP100² = 29.8 (IPCC AR6)

Hydrogen GWP100 = 11.6 (Nature 2023)

Densities at 1 bar, 15 °C:

- CH₄ = 0.656 kg/m³
- H₂ = 0.0899 kg/m³

Using an arbitrary methane -outflow:

Methane Q = 1.0 m³/h

Hydrogen Q = 2.5 m³/h (conservative value)

CO₂ equivalent calculation:

Methane

$$CO_{2eCH_4} = 0,656 \times 29,8 = 19,55 \text{ kg } CO_{2e}/h$$

Hydrogen

$$CO_{2eH_2} = 0,225 \times 11,6 = 2,61 \text{ kg } CO_{2e}/h$$

This implies that for the same hole size, the impact of hydrogen is approximately 13% of that of methane. If the GWP20 is used in the calculations, this is approximately 15%.

The lower CO₂ -equivalent emissions from hydrogen leaks do not constitute a direct reason to increase the leak detection frequency.

² Dutch natural gas consists of approximately 81% methane, 4% higher hydrocarbons, 1% CO₂, and 14% nitrogen.

6. What inspection policy for gas stations is necessary?

NEN 1059 [18] is the Dutch Standard for gas pressure regulating and metering stations for the transport and distribution of gases that comply with the Gas Quality Regulation. Hydrogen is not (yet) covered by this. This standard, which applies to a maximum upstream operating pressure of 100 bar (MOPu), also provides instructions for inspections, management, and maintenance. These descriptions are sufficiently general to be applicable to the operation of 8 bar and 16 bar hydrogen grids. NEN 1059 does not specify frequencies for inspections or maintenance. An interval must be chosen such that the safety risk of the station remains at an acceptable level.

It is recommended to inspect every type of hydrogen gas station (supplying from an 8 bar or 16 bar grid) at least annually. This represents an increase in the frequencies applied by regional grid operators at 8 bar natural gas stations. Further explanation follows below.

6.1 Differences between GRS and HRS

In a gas receiving station (GRS), gas is transferred from the national transmission grid to the natural gas distribution grid after pressure reduction (Maximum Operating Pressure of 8 bar). A hydrogen receiving station (HRS) performs more or less the same function, except that there is no national hydrogen transmission grid yet. In a HRS, for example, hydrogen is transferred from a tank to a distribution grid. In the case of hydrogen, a receiving station is also the location where the gas is odorized. Additionally, pressure reduction usually takes place in two steps. Consequently, in terms of control and monitoring, a HRS is generally more complex to operate compared to a GRS.

The site and building of a GRS are owned by a regional grid operator. The installation of a GRS is owned and managed by the national grid operator (Gasunie). For a HRS, this is currently different. A GRS is usually housed in a building, whereas the hydrogen receiving stations that Gasunie will realize are located outdoors. This has been done to increase safety.

6.2 Inspection and maintenance of natural gas stations

NEN 1059 provides guidelines for the operation and maintenance of gas pressure regulating stations. It states that a maintenance plan must be drawn up. NEN 1059 does not specify a frequency for inspections or maintenance, but indicates that an interval must be chosen for inspections such that the safety risk of the station is controlled to an acceptable level.

The standard describes a failure probability calculation to be applied as an aid in determining optimal inspection and maintenance intervals. Regional grid operators primarily use fixed frequencies for inspections and maintenance. See section 6.4

The specific implementation of the maintenance is left to the grid operator in NEN 1059. According to NEN 1059, there are different types of maintenance;

- a) Preventive maintenance;
 - a. Periodic preventive maintenance; replacement or overhaul of defect-free components
 - b. Condition-based maintenance; replacement or overhaul of defect-free parts based on, for example, a measurement performed during an **inspection**.
- b) Corrective maintenance; replacement or overhaul of components after detection of a functional defect
- c) Site maintenance; replacing, overhauling, or improving other components of the gas pressure regulating and metering station. This includes parts of the building or enclosure. Inspections include an assessment of gas tightness and the functioning of pressure regulation and pressure alarms.

NEN 1059 states that all equipment at the station must be maintained in such a way that it:

- a) offers sufficient operational reliability for the purpose for which it is used;
- b) is in good mechanical condition and does not leak;
- c) is adjusted to the correct pressure;
- d) is well protected against dirt, liquids, freezing, or other influences that could impair operation.

NEN 1059 states that the location and cabinet of the station must be maintained in such a way that:

- a) these are easily accessible under normal operating conditions and in emergency situations;
- b) inscriptions and signs are current and legible;
- c) the structural condition guarantees the proper and safe functioning of the gas installation until at least the next inspection

During the operation and maintenance of a gas station, maintenance activities performed and deviations must be recorded. If there are indications of deviations (such as excessively high or low gas pressure), the control and safety equipment must be inspected. If necessary, measures must be taken to rectify these deviations.

6.3 Inspection and maintenance of hydrogen gas stations

What has been stated above regarding natural gas stations can also be declared applicable to hydrogen gas stations. In line with the VIAG (Dutch Safety Instructions Natural Gas) and the associated Safety Work Instructions (SWIs), instructions have also been drawn up for working safely with hydrogen in the gas supply systems of the regional grid operators. These instructions indicate how the intended inspection and maintenance work can be carried out safely.

The VI-W (Dutch Safety Instructions Hydrogen) state that these instructions do not apply to the construction, management, and maintenance of a hydrogen injection plant. The pressures at an injection plant exceed 16 bar. Therefore, the DSO's are not formally permitted to maintain them either. Maintenance and operation are carried out by parties other than the DSO's.

A hydrogen feed-in installation consists of a buffer, a Hydrogen Receiving Station (HRS), and an odorization installation. The VI-W states that specific regulations apply per installation, which are not included in the VI-W.

The “VWI-H2-54-Safely commissioning and decommissioning hydrogen pressure regulating and measuring stations” identifies the additional and/or other risks that may occur during work on hydrogen gas stations. For each risk, specific measures to reduce the risk are specified. Examples include purging with nitrogen, using a thermal imaging camera, applying a flame arrester in the flare system, and using an oxygen concentration meter.

6.4 Frequency of inspection and maintenance

As mentioned earlier, the current NEN 1059 does not specify frequencies for conducting inspections and maintenance on gas stations. Depending on the type of gas station, the DSO's apply different frequencies for the inspections to be performed. There are also differences in the frequency of inspections among the DSO's. The table below indicates the range in which the inspections are carried out. As an example regarding B-inspections at High-Pressure Delivery Stations 10-40 m³/h (A9); there are DSO's that perform a B-inspection annually, but also grid operators that do not perform B-inspections at these stations or do so once every 5 years. For an explanation of the terms A, B, and C inspection, see the text-box on the next page.

Most DSO's only carry out maintenance if the results of the inspections warrant it. However, conducting inspections can also be considered a maintenance activity. For example, if a safety device is functionally tested, the intervention is in many cases made more operational.

Table 4; Range of frequencies used in conducting inspections at various gas stations

Type of pressure regulation station	Range of applied inspection frequencies as applied at Dutch DSO's					
	A-inspection		B-inspection		C-inspection	
GRS (site and building)	annual	1 time / 3 years	not applicable		not applicable	
Transfer station (OS)	annual	1 time / 2 years	annual	1 time / 2 year	1 time / 8 years	not
District station	annual		annual		1 time / 8 years	not
Main distribution station (supply to both HP and LP grids)	annual		annual		1 time / 8 years	not
Delivery station (category B or C)	1 time / 2 years	not	annual	once every 2 years	1 time / 8 years	not
Pressure monitoring station (biomethane feeders)	annual	not	annual		1 time / 8 years	not
High-pressure delivery station 10-40 m ³ /h (A9)	annual	1 time / 16 years	annual	not	1 time / 15 years	not
High-pressure delivery station up to 10 m ³ /h (A7 and A8)	annual	not	annual	not	1 time / 15 years	not
Open-ended delivery (meter and filter only) OEL	annual	not	1 time / 2 years	not	not	

What are A, B, and C inspections?

The terms A, B, and C inspections and associated minimum frequencies originate from the supplement to the Dutch NEN 1059 of 1994. The current NEN 1059 (2019) no longer mentions these terms and associated minimum frequencies. Because many DSO's still use these terms (partially), a brief explanation follows below, which has been adopted from the supplement to NEN 1059 dated 1994;

The A-inspection is a visual check during which no actions are performed on the control and metering station and the operation of the control line is not interrupted. If necessary, corrective maintenance follows from an A-inspection.

The B inspection is subdivided into a B1 inspection and a B2 inspection.

The B1 inspection is identical to the A inspection, but is extended to include a check on the functioning of the individual components. If necessary, corrective maintenance also follows from this.

The B2 inspection is a check on the proper indication of the compatible gas meter(s) and the volume conversion instrument.

The C-inspection is identical to the B-inspection, but is extended with an internal inspection and a partial overhaul of the individual components. If necessary, this results in corrective maintenance. The C-inspection does not apply to the gas meter and the volume conversion instrument.

C inspections are no longer carried out by most grid operators. However, the activities assigned to A and B inspections are performed by all grid operators.

During the transition to hydrogen, risks at gas stations will (potentially) change due to;

- A. a higher leakage rate in the event of a leak opening
- B. higher speeds with potentially more transport of dust or other effects of wear
- C. adhesion of safety devices
- D. change in natural frequency and stability of the controller

Limited information is available regarding aspects C and D in particular, and it is therefore unclear to what extent this could become a problem during prolonged use of the gas station with hydrogen.

Note regarding A

See the following paragraph for further explanation regarding the assessment of the technical gas tightness of the installation.

Note regarding B

Regarding dust transport, research has been conducted within the framework of HyDelta [19]. It is not a given fact that a higher hydrogen velocity will lead to increased dust transport. However, this may be the case during the initial start-up of the hydrogen flow rate. Any changes in flow directions during a conversion can also result in increased dust transport.

Note regarding C

Previous studies [20] [21] into the operation of hydrogen gas stations concluded that the assessed gas stations showed virtually no differences compared to operation on natural gas. Those reports mention that long-term effects were left out of consideration.

Note regarding D

Vibrations and stability of gas pressure regulators and the theoretical foundations are described in two articles [22] [23]. Based on these, the change from natural gas to hydrogen could affect the stability of the regulators.

Since there is currently limited experience with the long-term operation of hydrogen gas stations, it is advisable to carry out visual and functional inspections more frequently than usual during the first few years. This aligns with a remark in the current NEN 1059;

In the absence of information regarding failure frequencies, a period of one year applies to the inspection of the technical gas-tightness of the installation (up to 16 bar) and the functioning of pressure regulation and pressure alarm.

The performance of C-inspections (internal inspection and partial overhaul of individual components) is not considered necessary. However, these may be carried out if a functional test warrants it.

In the event of a potential conversion of a natural gas station to a hydrogen gas station, a suitability assessment must first take place prior to the conversion. This assessment falls outside the scope of this study (maintenance & operation). During this assessment, individual components will need to be evaluated, as well as, for example, the ventilation facilities. As stated in 7.1 it is advisable to enlarge the ventilation openings.

6.5 Leak tightness

During an inspection, a gas station is assessed for external and internal leakage. With the same leak opening, the hydrogen leakage rate will be higher than when operating on natural gas [24].

An assessment of the external leak tightness of a gas station will typically be carried out using leak detection spray and/or gas detectors. These methods are also applicable to hydrogen. A leak opening fed with hydrogen will be detected more quickly due to the higher flow rate compared to the same leak fed with natural gas. By applying the same leak tightness criteria to hydrogen (no bubble formation or a concentration < xxx ppm) as to natural gas, an equivalent level of safety is achieved.

An assessment of the internal leak tightness of control valves and safety shut-off valves is carried out by measuring a pressure rise in a specific enclosed pipe section. The various DSO's apply different limit values for this. The limit values used for natural gas can also be applied to hydrogen.

As an example; a grid operator currently applies a maximum pressure rise of 10 mbar in 1 minute as a limit value (for natural gas).

A closed safety valve may therefore exhibit an internal leakage that leads to a pressure rise of 10 mbar in one minute (pressure at the inlet side of the valve is 8 bar, the pressure at the outlet side of the valve to be assessed up to the next valve is atmospheric). If this valve with internal leakage is set to hydrogen, the leakage rate increases (theoretically by a factor of 1.2 to 3, see [24]). Consequently, more hydrogen flows into the closed pipe section during one minute of assessment, and as a result, the pressure will rise more rapidly. By applying the same maximum pressure rise in a specific period, the acceptable leakage openings are smaller, but the limit for the maximum hydrogen leakage rate remains the same as for natural gas.

6.6 Permeation in a gas station

In a dual-branched gas station as part of the pilot project in Wagenborgen (The Netherlands), an investigation was conducted into the permeation of oxygen in the section downstream of the pressure regulator in the standby-branch. Oxygen permeation occurs via the membrane or membranes of the regulator. In the supplying branch, this limited amount of oxygen is discharged into the daily gas flow and will not lead to a flammable mixture.

In the section of piping immediately after the regulator in the reserve line, there is theoretically a risk of stagnant gas.

Conservative calculations show that a flammable mixture may form directly downstream of the controller after approximately 80 days. These calculations assume that no diffusion or mixing occurs. In practice, this will occur to a greater or lesser extent. It is expected that no flammable mixture will form. This may be confirmed by the measurements performed at Wagenborgen. This report is expected to be submitted to Netbeheer Nederland in April 2026.

6.7 The MOP and the MIP

When choosing a 16 bar hydrogen grid, the value for the maximum operating pressure (the MOP; Maximum Operating Pressure) must be clear. This refers to the maximum pressure at which the gas distribution system can function continuously under normal operating conditions. Based on the chosen MOP value, the maximum incidental pressure (MIP; Maximum Incidental Pressure) is calculated. This pressure is a fixed factor higher than the MOP, where this factor depends on the pressure range of the MOP.

If the pressure in a 16 bar hydrogen grid must never exceed 16 bar, the MIP must be 16 bar or lower. As a result of this choice, the MOP has a value of 12.3 bar (based on Table 5 of NEN 1059:2019).

If the pressure may occasionally exceed 16 bar, a Maximum Operating Pressure (MOP) of 16 bar can be selected. The MMIP for this choice is then 20.8 bar (based on Table 5 of NEN 1059:2019). Standard NEN 7244-1 [25] applies to pipelines with a maximum operating pressure of up to and including 16 bar. The same standard describes that the maximum operating pressure corresponds to the term MOP. Based on NEN 7244-1, the choice of a MOP of 16 bar is possible.

The settings of safety valves in the operating branch and if applicable standby-branch must be such that the MIP is not exceeded, taking into account the tolerances of the safety valves.

7. What about ATEX inspections?

In the current gas distribution grid, ATEX legislation applies to various parts of the gas infrastructure, particularly the gas pressure regulating (and metering) stations (PRS/ PRM). The application of ATEX regulations is primarily intended as a control measure in the event of a potential leak at such a gas pressure regulating station. The instrumentation which is installed within the PRS shall be suitable for the zone which it is placed in. The underlying principle has always been that the lower flammability limit must not be exceeded in the case of a regular leak.

To what extent are maintenance and operation activities related to ATEX regulations, different from the transition to 8 or 16 bar hydrogen grids?

The ATEX inspections at 8 bar or 16 bar hydrogen gas stations are expected to be carried out with the same frequency as the inspections at 8 bar natural gas stations. The focus points for these inspections are of the same design. However, differences may arise in content between the ATEX inspections at hydrogen stations and natural gas stations. This follows from the initial ATEX assessment.

7.1 Zone classification according to IEC60079 in relation to ventilation

Currently, the cabinets of natural gas pressure regulating stations are largely classified as Zone 2, which is determined based on various boundary conditions in line with the NPR7910 and/or IEC60079-10-1. The choice of boundary conditions during the transition to hydrogen (8 bar or 16 bar) will determine whether this will remain the same.

During HyDelta 2, the role of ventilation in gas pressure regulating station cabinets was extensively examined [26] one of the crucial boundary conditions for determining the ATEX zoning. Based on various boundary conditions (such as the leakage rate), while maintaining the same zone classification, it is advisable to enlarge the ventilation openings to minimize accumulation within the enclosure as much as possible [27].

The assumptions regarding a realistic leakage rate must be determined based on the technical details of the gas pressure regulating station. For instance, a higher leakage rate may lead to the need to zone the ventilation openings as well, as a result of the expected equilibrium concentration within the cabinet. Since the basis of a gas pressure regulating station is a leak-tight installation (according to the definition of “enhanced tightness” according to EN1127-1 (annex B3)), it is expected that the frequency of ATEX inspections will not need to change. This follows from the assumption that the installation is and remains sufficiently leak-tight between the various maintenance services.

When repurposing a gas pressure regulating station, an owner is required to demonstrate the suitability of the installation. The normative IEC 60079 series provides extensive information regarding explosion safety and the application of this standard. This series can be effectively used for both new construction and repurposing. In this context, a number of standards will be of essential importance. The various situations are explained in the diagram below;

Figure 4; flowchart for applying the 60079 series

7.2 New hydrogen gas station

For a new gas pressure regulation installation for an 8 bar or 16 bar hydrogen distribution grid, an ATEX dossier (containing, for example, an EVD) must be compiled. This ATEX assessment will then result in points of attention applicable to ATEX inspections, such as the suitability of the installation and the safety of the electrical installation. This dossier must be able to demonstrate suitability before the installation is placed. This document also specifies how inspections are handled. After installation, the frequency of inspections of the installation will essentially be structured similarly to that of ATEX inspections of gas pressure regulation stations (using natural gas). In the event of an inspection, consideration may be given to the condition of the cabinet, the station dossier, the electrical installation (if present), lighting (if present), telemetry (if present), gas meter, EVHI, and communication unit (if present).

7.3 Conversion of an existing station

When repurposing an existing natural gas station into an 8 bar or 16 bar hydrogen station, it must be determined whether the existing station is suitable for the intended application. This involves an assessment in accordance with the NEN 1059. Part of this involves demonstrating and assessing explosion safety. As with a new station, this results in the points of attention for future ATEX inspections.

7.4 Inspection and maintenance

When maintenance is performed on a gas pressure regulating station, the type of maintenance will determine exactly which measures must be applied. In the case of a B-inspection, for example testing the functionality of the safety devices within the gas pressure regulating station, the ATEX zoning will be maintained. If, for example, a gas pressure regulator needs to be replaced, the gas pressure regulating station will be blocked off, depressurized, and made gas-free. After the installation has been made gas-free, the ATEX zoning can be (temporarily) removed. Naturally, work instructions will

be drawn up for this, assessing the necessity for wearing PPE and/or a hydrogen detector. This may be required to detect the possibility of gas leakage at an early stage.

7.5 Use of electronic equipment

The use of standard electronic equipment can, in the event of a leak, act as an ignition source [28]. When the zoning within a gas pressure regulating station is removed, electronic equipment (for instance a mobile phone) could theoretically be used without risk. At that specific moment, provided there is proper ventilation and verification using PPE, this poses no imminent threat. This could be indicated in the updated work plan, in case of for instance the decommissioning of a pressure reducing station (VIAG, G-54). The question is whether one should wish to do such a thing, given the risk of confusing a secured environment (with temporary no ATEX) with a gas pressure regulating installation in normal operation (ATEX environment).

A comprehensive explanation regarding ATEX regulations concerning the switching of gas type and/or pressure is included in Annex II

8. Does the gas quality of hydrogen need to be monitored additionally?

Due to the significant influence of contaminants on gas quality and the stricter requirements imposed on hydrogen compared to natural gas, hydrogen quality must be monitored more closely. Other parameters must be taken into account, and the limit values for those parameters will also be different. A 16 bar hydrogen grid requires no additional monitoring beyond that of an 8 bar hydrogen grid. The pressure difference has no influence on the parameters that need to be monitored, and is expected to have minimal or no effect on the limit values of those parameters.

It is recommended to install additional monitoring at sensitive end users. When very strict requirements are imposed on certain parameters, for example a maximum O₂ level of 5 ppm for fuel cells, it is advisable to have continuous monitoring of this parameter be performed at the customer's premises. The question is whether this additional monitoring should be the responsibility of the grid operator. Grid operators will guarantee a certain degree of purity. Should a customer desire purer hydrogen, it stands to reason that this customer will perform additional metering and, where necessary, purification themselves.

The contaminants considered here result from permeation or contamination from existing natural gas pipelines. Contamination caused by pipeline rupture and contamination during construction/maintenance are excluded from consideration, as they do not affect the chemical composition of the gas. These contaminants will be captured by filters. Contamination resulting from hydrogen production (at the injection point) is described in Chapter 9.

Changes in the chemical composition of hydrogen gas have a relatively much greater impact than is the case with natural gas. An important reason for this is the relatively very low density of hydrogen compared to most other components.

A minimum purity of 98% hydrogen is generally considered a requirement for hydrogen quality. If more impurities are permitted, the potential range of the Wobbe index becomes too wide. Gas appliances can only handle a limited Wobbe range; outside that range, a burner will not be able to function (optimally). Exceeding or falling below the Wobbe index range poses a risk of flashback, blow-offs, and incomplete combustion. This applies to both natural gas and hydrogen appliances.³ Within Hydelta 3 WP1a, a techno-economic evaluation was conducted regarding the optimal purity of hydrogen in regional grids. The outcome was that the optimal purity lies between 98% and 99.5% hydrogen [29].

Gas quality requirements can vary significantly depending on the type of customer. For example, hydrogen intended for fuel cells must meet extremely high standards, and hydrogen used as a feedstock also has stringent requirements. Purification plants will be required at injection points or at specific customers. It is important to make clear agreements regarding this in advance and to clearly define whose responsibility this concerns. Depending on the application, an odorant may also be considered a contaminant.

³ A gas appliance must be specifically suitable for hydrogen. Although the Wobbe index for hydrogen may fall within the range of the Wobbe index for natural gas, appliances must be specifically suitable for operation on hydrogen, partly due to the increased risk of flashback.

8.1 Pollution by permeation

The risk of off-spec gas resulting from intrusion of contaminants due to permeation during distribution depends on the pipe material, the pipe dimensions, the pressure inside the pipe and temperature of the grid. The influence of these factors is explained further in the remainder of this chapter. For pressures above 1 barg, the effect of permeation will be limited, according to modeling in Hydelta 3 WP1a.2 [29].

Contaminants as present during hydrogen injection are discussed in Chapter 9.

Piping material

Steel or plastic pipes can be used for the transport of hydrogen. With steel pipes, the influence of gas permeation through the pipe wall is negligible. With plastic pipes, however, this does play a role. The rate at which gas permeates through a material is called the permeability coefficient. The permeability coefficient is a property of the material independent of the dimensions of the pipe, but strongly dependent on the type of permeate and the temperature. For example, the oxygen permeability coefficient for PE around room temperature is between 38.9 -77.7 (ml·mm)/(m²·day·bar) and for PVC it is 4.6-19.1 (ml·mm)/(m²·day·bar) [30].

Pipe dimensions

Permeation is strongly dependent on the dimensions of the pipe. A larger diameter results in a bigger surface area that gas can permeate through and thus a higher amount permeating. At the same time, a thicker pipe wall results in less permeation. The permeation stays the same for the same ratio between diameter and wall thickness (the SDR, which stand for “Standard Dimension Ratio”).

Pipes with larger diameters will experience a relatively less contamination due to permeation. Because of the relatively larger volume of the gas, there is less of an effect on the gas quality. Additionally, it should be noted that the pipe diameter is matched to the demand, ensuring continuous replenishment.

A potential disadvantage of a thicker pipe wall is that more contaminants can be absorbed into the wall during prolonged transport of natural gas. When these pipes are reused, this can result in contaminants escaping from the pipe wall for longer.

Pressure

Higher pressure will lead to an increase in the permeation rate from inside to outside the pipe. This will have no effect on the permeation rate of gasses from outside permeating into the pipe, because the partial pressures of these gasses stay the same. However, higher pressure does ensure that the effect of permeation on gas quality is smaller. At higher pressures, there is a relatively larger amount of gas in the pipe. Relatively speaking, the permeated contaminants will then constitute a smaller proportion of the total gas. This applies only to pipes with the same dimensions and the same pipe material.

Temperature

The permeation rate of gas through plastic pipes increases with increasing temperature. There is experimental evidence that hydrogen follows the Arrhenius equation for hydrogen [31]. For other gasses this is assumed to be the same.

The temperature of the soil at a depth of 1 meter varies little, between 5°C and 18°C [31]. Permeation experiments are often conducted at room temperature and as such can be considered as a worst case scenario.

8.2 Contamination from repurposed pipes

The choice between new or repurposed pipelines for the transport of hydrogen can have a significant impact on gas quality. Plastic pipelines previously used for the transport of natural gas are saturated with impurities from natural gas (alkanes and aromatics) and with the odorant tetrahydrothiophene (THT). PE pipelines and, to a lesser extent, PVC pipelines can continue to release THT into the gas for a very long time [32].

Contaminants can also bind to the walls of steel pipes. However, this primarily concerns THT located on the surface of the pipe material. After thorough purging several times, it is therefore expected that no further problems will be experienced in this regard [33]. At higher temperatures, relatively more contamination is released from the pipe surface and from the pipe material. At higher pressures (16 bar) there will not be an increase in the amount of contaminants released; instead, the contamination is distributed over a larger normal volume of gas. While a larger pipe diameter does result in more contamination, this is also distributed over a proportionally larger amount of gas.

8.3 Odorization of hydrogen

Odorization, the addition of an odorant, of gas is an important safety measure to enable timely leakage detection, especially for odorless flammable gases. For this reason, tetrahydrothiophene (THT) has been added to natural gas for decades in the Netherlands. Odorization is also being considered for hydrogen. Research within Hydelta has shown that THT is suitable for the odorization of hydrogen [34]. THT is a sulfur compound, which entails two disadvantages:

1. It is harmful to certain end users of hydrogen. Fuel cells have extremely low sulfur tolerances, with a recommended limit of 4 ppb (parts per billion). Certain chemical reaction catalysts are also sensitive to sulfur.
2. Combustion produces SO_2 , which conflicts with the increasingly strict emission requirements of, among others, the transport sector.

In current pilot projects, THT is used as an odorant. When odorization with THT is chosen, it will need to be removed again (deodorization) at sensitive end users. Methods for removing small amounts of sulfur compounds are largely still under development [35]. The most mature and, for the time being, one of the most effective methods is Pressure Swing Absorption (PSA) [36]. This method is effective for removing a large amount of contaminants, but has the disadvantages that some hydrogen is lost as 'tail gas', that it is mainly applicable to large volumes of hydrogen, and that a significant pressure reduction occurs, with an outgoing pressure of approximately one-fourth of the incoming pressure. Other purification methods that may potentially be applied in the future for the removal of sulfur odorants are membrane separation, metal hydride separation, and catalytic purification. Each of these methods has the potential to produce very pure hydrogen without the large losses seen with PSA and is also specifically applicable to smaller volumes.

An advantage of choosing THT as an odorant is that the desorption of THT in repurposed pipes is no longer a problem.

The possibilities for an alternative odorant are also being explored. Research into alternative odorants has already been conducted within Hydelta 1 WP 2. GASODOR S-FREE and 2-hexyne were mentioned there as alternatives to THT; at concentrations comparable to THT, these also produced comparable odor strengths and characteristics in hydrogen [34]. Regarding GASODOR S-FREE, questions remain about the effectiveness of the odorant, as many people associated the smell with something that was not alarming ('paint' is a frequently used description of the smell) [37]. For the time being, 2-hexyne is considered a possible alternative, as small-scale tests classify it as alarming and as comparable in smell to THT. Further research is needed into, among other things, the stability, safety, and effectiveness of 2-hexyne.

Research into sulfur-free alternatives to THT has not yet been completed, and only GASODOR S-FREE is currently available on the market. Chevron Phillips Chemicals is currently developing its own sulfur-free odorant, Scintinel H2. It is expected that this will be ready for market within a few years. A pilot project is currently underway at Stedin (Power2Gas, Rozenburg, running from June 2025 to March 2026).

A final option is to replace odorization with other safety measures. However, there are no good (proven) alternatives that can be applied as widely. The built environment, in particular, poses a significant risk. In homes, it is difficult to cost-effectively apply a technology that guarantees the same level of safety as odorization. Sensors require installation and regular maintenance, which would be extremely labor-intensive for individual homes. At the same time, the effectiveness of odorization is actually highest in indoor installations, where soil absorption of the odorant plays no role and the frequency with which people are nearby to detect the odorant is highest.

Failure to odorize without an effective countermeasure can increase the likelihood that a gas leak leads to a serious incident by a factor of 50 in the case of natural gas. There is no reason to assume that this likelihood will be lower for hydrogen. The dangers of failure to odorize are described in detail in Hydelta 1 WP2 D2.4 [38].

8.4 Additional monitoring of gas quality

Due to stricter gas quality requirements, additional monitoring is necessary. This additional monitoring can take two forms. Firstly, additional checks at consumers to prevent the gas grid's influence on gas quality from affecting it to such an extent that it falls outside the specifications. Secondly, increased monitoring of the injected gas quality more in line with the procedures for biomethane.

Regarding the additional checks, a choice can be made to always monitor gas quality at customers, or only at customers for whom high gas quality is critical. A third option is the use of analyzers at strategically chosen locations in combination with a computational model to calculate gas quality throughout the entire grid. TNO is currently developing a smart gas grid model called AURORA as part of the SHIMMER project – Safe Hydrogen. Injection Modeling and Management for European gas grid Resilience [39]– and a sensor placement algorithm, Astraia, as part of Hydelta [40]. Within these tracks, the focus was on the smart placement of pressure sensors to obtain the most accurate possible picture of the pressure distribution across a gas grid. Simulations of the gas grid are performed using AURORA. Astraia then calculates the optimal sensor placement.

Additional monitoring during injection is also desirable. The risk of incorrect injection will be higher for hydrogen due to the following factors;

- the hydrogen market is still in development
- the arrival of new production techniques
- a multitude of parties that can be producers
- a variation in the experience of producers

It is therefore recommended that the methodology currently applied to biomethane injection also be applied to injectors in hydrogen transport grids. This is discussed further in Chapter 9.

9. Is there a difference in gas quality when fed in by HNS and other suppliers?

With supply by HNS (top-down), hydrogen of a more consistent quality can be expected compared to other suppliers (bottom-up). The supply of hydrogen by HNS to the distribution companies can be monitored in the same way as is currently done for the supply of natural gas by Gasunie. This methodology does not need to change in the event of a pressure increase to 16 bar.

For the supply of hydrogen by smaller suppliers (not HNS), a methodology for monitoring gas quality can be applied as is currently done for biomethane injection.

This entails;

- 1) Continuous monitoring by the biomethane supplier
- 2) Periodic check (e.g. once a month) of THT concentration and olfactory testing by an external party
- 3) Periodic inspection (e.g. once every six months) of gas quality and inspection of the gas chromatograph by an external party

Currently, an evaluation of the monitoring of gas quality during biomethane injection is underway. The methodology mentioned above is not expected to change in this regard.

Further explanation follows in the rest of this chapter.

9.1 The hydrogen transport grid

Hydrogen Grid Services (HNS) has been appointed as the grid operator of the national hydrogen transport grid. The goal of this grid is to connect suppliers with five major industrial clusters where there is large-scale demand for hydrogen. Additionally, the hydrogen transport grid will connect the Netherlands to other countries. This is comparable to Gasunie's current transport grid. The hydrogen transport grid will consist (partly) of repurposed Gasunie pipelines [41]. This involves steel pipelines that previously carried natural gas.

The hydrogen transport grid can be viewed as one large supplier. The transport grid itself also has suppliers of various possible types, as shown below. The main difference between the transport grid and other suppliers on a distribution grid is the stability of the gas quality of the supplied hydrogen. Due to the large volumes, the potential mixing of hydrogen from different suppliers, and the control measures that HNS itself will implement, the likelihood of HNS hydrogen quality deviating significantly from quality requirements is smaller than with other suppliers on the distribution grid. This will primarily affect the risk analysis of off-spec gas, where a lower frequency may possibly be assumed. However, if the volume of consumption is significantly higher than at other suppliers, the impact will be greater.

Another difference compared to other suppliers is that HNS can be both a supplier and a consumer. This requires bidirectional gas quality monitoring and likely additional purification (such as the removal of sulfur odorant, if used in the distribution grid; see sub-question 7). It is advisable to entrust the execution and maintenance in both directions to the same party, due to the complexity of the management.

Figure 5 Schematic representation of the current plans for the hydrogen transport grid in The Netherlands

9.2 Expected contaminations associated with the production process

Research is currently being conducted into a wide range of potential hydrogen production methods. Depending on the process, various impurities are generated during this process [36] [42]. These impurities are risk factors for gas quality if insufficient purification takes place. Therefore, the presence of these impurities must be strictly monitored at the hydrogen injection site. The measurement method may vary depending on the type of impurity. The following types of contaminations are expected on the national and/or regional hydrogen grids depending on the type of production process of the suppliers:

Contaminants	Identification of Source
N₂, O₂, H₂O, Ar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All methods of hydrogen production
He	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All methods using natural gas as feedstock (not applicable to methods in which He was removed from the gas during the process)
NH₃	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NH₃ production process in which excess hydrogen is generated Biogas reforming Coal gasification producing hydrogen as a byproduct The method of producing H₂ with hydrazine
Halogen compounds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A chlor alkali process producing excess hydrogen (excluding methods using ion exchange membranes) Hydrogen production from biogas produced from waste containing plastics Coke oven gas Water electrolysis (only where water quality is not guaranteed in the process by adequate treatment)
Total sulphur compounds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steam reforming (the sulphur compounds present in the process are only H₂S) Catalytic reforming Partial oxidation Auto-thermal reforming Coal gasification (where hydrogen is a byproduct) Hydrogen production methods where sulphur compounds are used for gas odorization
Total hydrocarbons excluding methane	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All production methods that use fossil fuels
CO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steam reforming Catalytic reforming Reforming Partial oxidation Auto-thermal reforming Coal gasification (hydrogen is a byproduct)
HCHO, HCOOH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other than steam reforming, methods of hydrogen production using crude oil as fuel (steam reforming was excluded because the HCHO and HCOOH contents of the products of this process were found to be significantly lower than specified in the standards)

Figure 6; Table 3-2 from [42] type of contaminations are depending on type of production process of supplier

The hydrogen quality requirements for the hydrogen transport grid have not been established at the time of writing this report [44].

Due to the linkage with foreign grids and the wide variety of different suppliers, establishing gas quality requirements for the transmission grid is a complex issue [43]. Ideally, the whole of Europe would have the same purity requirements for hydrogen, so that no purification is required at borders. However, the optimal purity for hydrogen depends on the types, composition, and location of both the suppliers and end users. Electrolyzer operators benefit from a high purity requirement because their process already produces very pure hydrogen. SMR produces much less pure hydrogen, making a lower purity requirement advantageous for them in order to minimize the amount of purification they need to perform themselves.

On the user side, the mobility sector demands high standards to minimize the need for purification itself. In contrast, gas engines and turbines are less critical for which purity matters. For those end users, higher standards simply mean more expensive hydrogen than necessary.

The current trade-off being made involves a purity requirement of 98% or 99.5%. This is equivalent to the recommendation for regional grids in Hydelta 3 WP1a.2 [29]. That recommendation assumes a hydrogen purity of 99.5% for the HNS, where the purity of the national hydrogen transport grid serves as the upper limit for the recommended purity of regional grids. In a situation where hydrogen taken from the HNS requires additional purification before being admitted to the regional grid, significant extra purification costs are involved. It is therefore advisable never to set quality requirements for regional grids stricter than those for the HNS.

9.3 The influence of pressure increases

The compression of gas in general, and thereby also hydrogen, using mechanical compressors typically affects purity [45]. An article in Plant Engineering states that regarding air compression, contamination concerns the ppm level of oil aerosols in the case of oil-lubricated compressors [46]. In the case of compressors that are not oil-lubricated, the concentration is less than 0.1 ppm [46]. In the case of compressed air, contamination with particles of carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides, and sulfur dioxide is also present [46]. However, since no outside air is drawn in during hydrogen compression, it is unlikely that this is also an issue with hydrogen. As no direct literature has been found regarding the contamination of hydrogen during compression, it is recommended to investigate this further.

Pressure swing adsorption (PSA) is the primary technique used in industry to purify hydrogen [47]. Because hydrogen purification using PSA is more effective at higher pressures, it is advisable to compress first and only then increase the purity. [47] Currently, this sequence is also applied in the upgrading of biogas to biomethane before it is injected into the grid [48]. Hydrogen produced by electrolysis, however, inherently possesses such purity that any contamination from compressors is indeed relevant if it still needs to be purified afterwards [49].

9.4 Current handling of natural gas

Natural gas in the Netherlands is currently only supplied top-down. Natural gas is fed into Gasunie's high-pressure transport grid, the HTL grid. Depending on the source, the quality of the natural gas is adjusted. For instance, most modern sources, such as natural gas from the North Sea, England, Norway, or from LNG tankers, have an H-gas quality. However, this has a much higher Wobbe index than the G-gas that most end users are accustomed to. H-gas is therefore mixed with nitrogen before being delivered as G-gas to the distribution grids.

Gas quality checks are in the current system carried out by Gasunie at injection points, mixing stations, metering and control stations, and gas receiving stations. The first three are part of Gasunie's transport grid; the fourth is the transfer point from the transport grid to a distribution grid. The results obtained by Gasunie, Gasunie's work instructions, and the gas quality are checked on a sample basis by DNV and Kiwa Technology.

No further checks take place in the distribution grid. Gasunie has years of experience transporting natural gas, which reduces the risk of off-spec gas. This knowledge will be partially transferable to the management of the hydrogen transport grid by subsidiary HNS.

9.5 Current handling of biomethane injection

In the current natural gas system, biomethane is injected into primarily 8-bar distribution grids and, in a few cases, the 40-bar regional transport grid. This must be of equal quality to the G-gas supplied by Gasunie. A 'gatekeeper' is located before the biomethane injection point; this system checks the gas quality using gas chromatographs. If a set value is exceeded, a three-way valve closes, thereby stopping the injection into the gas grid. The gas flow is then routed back into the installation. The gatekeeper is located before the odorization system, meaning the THT content is not checked. The main reason for this is that sulfur compounds are toxic to the microbes in a fermentation plant, which is currently the most common form of biomethane production.

Behind the odorization system, there are sometimes a siphon and a pressure monitoring station. A siphon collects liquid from the gas to protect the gas grid against condensate formed during the biomethane production process that has not been sufficiently captured in the purification plant, and against liquid THT that may be released due to a malfunction of the odorization pump. The pressure monitoring station is located between the production plant and the transfer point. It monitors, regulates, and/or controls the pressure and serves as a sampling point [50].

With biomethane, the most common reason for off-spec gas in the gas grid is the failure of the odorization system, because it is located behind the three-way valve, meaning there are no additional safety limits. Consequently, grid operators have specific work instructions on how to deal with over- and under-odorization (see Enexis as an example) [51]. It is expected that this approach will be similar for hydrogen grids. The risks of over- and under-odorization are no different than with natural gas and biomethane. However, it is assumed that hydrogen quality is additionally monitored at the point of delivery for critical end users.

For biomethane, the (measurement) responsibility for supplying the correct gas quality and quantity lies with the supplier, while the grid operator is tasked with ensuring compliance with the required quality specifications [52]. This system is also recommended for hydrogen.

The oversight on the gas quality of the biomethane supplier is currently carried out in three ways:

1. Continuous monitoring by the gatekeeper with a built-in gas chromatograph. The main components of the biomethane, such as methane, CO₂, nitrogen, oxygen, the water content, and H₂S, are measured, and the Wobbe index is determined from this
2. Monthly check of the THT concentration and odor by an external party
3. Semi-annual inspection of all gas quality requirements and inspection of the gas chromatograph's operation by an external party

Such a method of control will also be necessary in the case of hydrogen. Continuous monitoring of the main components and Wobbe index is important for all end users. However, which components need to be monitored may differ, also based on the production process, see Figure 5. Continuous monitoring of all possible contaminants is not realistic. Accurately measuring some trace components requires advanced equipment and specialized knowledge, which could limit access to the hydrogen grid to only the largest suppliers. The measurement of those trace components will have to be carried out periodically by a specialized laboratory.

The handling of odorization is expected to remain the same, at least initially. Checking for odor is currently not something that can be automated, meaning it must be checked semi-regularly by an independent party. It should be noted, however, that the risk of odor deviations with hydrogen is likely to be lower than with biomethane and may depend heavily on the production process. In the case of an electrolyzer, for example, no odor deviations are expected other than due to a deviation in the amount of THT.

Supervision of continuous monitoring may need to be enforced more strictly. For example, the influence of composition on the Wobbe index is much greater for hydrogen than for biomethane, due to the much lower density of hydrogen. Most hydrogen specifications therefore assume a minimum of 98% hydrogen to limit the variation in the bandwidth of the Wobbe index.

9.6 The quality demands of end users

If the quality requirements of specific end users are not met, there is a risk that they will choose not to be connected to the hydrogen grid, but instead obtain hydrogen through other means, or cease their business operations or relocate altogether. However, if the grid quality requirements are too strict, unnecessarily high grid costs will arise for all connected parties. This, in turn, creates the risk that end users with low quality demand will not wish to participate. Establishing quality requirements for hydrogen grids, for both distribution and transport, thus becomes a complex issue.

The quality requirements of end users depend heavily on the type of end user. The end-use of hydrogen can be roughly divided into three categories:

- Fuel cells: The highest quality requirements are applied to this hydrogen
- As a feedstock: High quality requirements are also applied to this. Hydrogen is widely used in chemical processes. In some processes, impurities can result in the poisoning of catalysts
- Burners, gas engines, and gas turbines: There are no strict requirements regarding gas quality for these. The main limiting factor is the Wobbe index. To prevent the Wobbe index from fluctuating too much, the purity must be at least 98%

Figure 7 provides an overview of the various specifications for end users from HyDelta 3 WP1a.

Category		HNS entry specification (proposal)	Industry Feedstock (methanol)	Mobility, Built environment, CHP	Industry heating processes	Mobility	Power generation	Built environment
Technology		-	Catalyst	Fuel cells	Burners	Gas engines	Gas engines, gas turbines	Burners
H ₂ purity (%)	High	98	96.5	99.95	98			
	Low	99.5	99.9	99.99	98			
Max. Hydrocarbons (C _n H _n) [mol%]		0.5 (9.5%) – 1.5 (98%)	3	-	Determined by Wobbe Index			
Max. inerts (N ₂ , Ar, He) [mol%]		0.5 (9.5%) – 2.0 (98%)	0.5	0.05	Determined by Wobbe Index			
CO [ppm]		≤ 20	-	-	≤ 0.8			
CO ₂ [ppm]		≤ 20	-	≤ 1000	Determined by Wobbe Index			
Total sulphur [ppm]		≤ 3	≤ 0.05	≤ 0.004	≤ 7.3 (peak value) ≤ 3.9 (year average)			
Formaldehyde [ppm]		≤ 10	-	≤ 0.01	≤ 10			
Formic acid [ppm]		≤ 10	-	≤ 0.2	≤ 10			
Ammonia [ppm]		≤ 10	-	≤ 0.1	≤ 10			
Hydrogen chloride [ppm]		-	≤ 10	-	-	-	-	-
Sodium hydroxide [ppm]		-	-	≤ 0.1	-	-	-	-
Total halogens (Cl, Br, F) [ppm]		≤ 50	≤ 0.001	≤ 0.05	≤ 3.1			
Oxygen [ppm]		≤ 10	≤ 10	≤ 500	≤ 1700			
Solid particles [µg/l, 20°C, 1 bar]		-	-	≤ 1	-	-	-	-

Figure 7: Overview of quality requirements of different types of end users from HyDelta 3 WP1a

In particular, the quality requirements for fuel cells are so high that they cannot possibly be taken as a standard for the entire hydrogen grid [43] [29]. There are various possible solutions for end users with fuel cells. Firstly, additional purification can be applied at the customer's site. Secondly, use can be made of subgrids with different quality requirements, whereby high-quality suppliers are coupled with customers with high quality requirements. Thirdly, the end-user can obtain hydrogen via transport methods other than the gas grid, for example tube trailers.

10. What additional conditions/risks are involved in operating 16 bar hydrogen gas grids?

Before a hydrogen distribution grid is operated at 16 bar, several basic conditions must be met. Additionally, risks may increase. To keep or reduce the risks during maintenance and operation to an acceptable level, measuring instruments and equipment must be able to withstand a pressure of 16 bar. Measures to reduce the **probability** of hazards occurring when operating a 16 bar distribution grid, as well as to mitigate the potential **impact** of those hazards, are largely similar to the measures employed when operating an 8 bar hydrogen distribution grid. In most cases, larger safety distances are required for a 16 bar grid because leakage rates can be higher. The suitability of the measuring instruments and equipment will need to be determined in further detail.

10.1 Conditions prior to commissioning

Important conditions for maintaining and operating 16 bar hydrogen grids are:

- The distribution grid used has been deemed suitable in advance for operation at 16 bar hydrogen
- The applied distribution grid may formally be operated at a MOP of 16 bar (see paragraph 6.7).
- Construction of new grids in accordance with Dutch NEN 7244 and NEN 1059; this series of standards and standard are supplemented with regard to hydrogen.
- The guidelines for newly constructed hydrogen grids with a pressure of up to 8 bar have been extended to applications up to 16 bar. The guidelines for pressures up to 8 bar are currently being drafted.
- The Safety Instructions Hydrogen (VI-W) and the Work Safety Instructions (VWIs) have been extended to applications up to 16 bar. See H1 for further explanation.
- Grid operators may need to prepare for the use of different piping materials. For the time being, steel will be used as piping material for a 16 bar grid, but other types of materials are also conceivable in the future (see HyDelta 4 report D2C.1). The current grids being constructed are mostly PE; a change in the piping material to be used may require organizational changes.

Some points of attention when drafting the guidelines for new hydrogen grids to be constructed (8 bar or 16 bar);

- Do not install a gas receiving station in a building, but in open space.
- Use as few flanges as possible (this reduces the risk of leaks).
- Ensure sufficient valve diagrams are available to enable sectioning and purging.

10.2 Risks may increase

A risk is defined as the **probability** of a hazard multiplied by the **impact** of that hazard. In the Risk Analysis methodology used by the DSO's (Fine & Kinney), exposure is also included. The risk of the hazard is then: probability of a hazard * exposure to that hazard * effect of that hazard. When operating a 16 bar distribution grid, the hazards do not change compared to operating an 8 bar distribution grid. The effects, however, may be different, which could lead to a higher risk. In Chapter 1 (Table 2), the risks that may increase with the raise from 8 to 16 bar have been identified. For example, the risk of uncontrolled hydrogen outflow or fire and explosion hazards will increase in a 16 bar grid because;

- a leakage rate in a 16 bar pipe be greater.
- the chance of ignition is greater (larger gas cloud, more energy from passing debris, less ignition energy needed)

To reduce the risks, various measures are applied. These are preventive measures to thereby reduce the likelihood of the hazard occurring. However, they are also protective measures to reduce the impact of the occurring hazard. As mentioned in Chapter 1, it must be determined for each activity in the described Safety Work Instruction whether the risk of that activity reaches an acceptable level with the relevant measure(s). In general, the points of attention regarding the various measures are listed below.

Table 5 Difference in measures to be taken to reduce risks when operating a 16 bar grid compared to an 8 bar grid.

Risk of hazard	Measures as specified in the VWIs	Possible difference of 16 bar with 8 bar
Presence of people and/or animals in the immediate vicinity of the workplace or the outlet opening of the vent or flare unit.	Shield the workplace and maintain adequate supervision of the outlet of gas release. People and/or animals should leave the workplace and surrounding area.	Ensure that blow-off and flare systems, including the flame arrester, are suitable for hydrogen and a pressure of 16 bar. Maintain larger safety distances.
Uncontrolled release of hydrogen into the open air.	Ventilate the workplace. Continue measuring the hydrogen concentration at all times. If the hydrogen concentration is > 0.4% (10% LEL), leave the workplace immediately. Report this to the Workplace Supervisor.	Maintain larger safety distances.
Uncontrolled release of hydrogen indoors.	Ventilate the workplace. Continuously monitor the hydrogen concentration. If the hydrogen concentration is > 0.4% (10% LEL), close the main valve if applicable and leave the workplace immediately. Report this to the Work Supervisor.	Maintain larger safety distances.
Invisible hydrogen flame, e.g. at the flare unit or unexpected ignition.	Use a thermal imaging camera when using the (mini) flare unit or approaching incidents.	Ensure that venting and flaring systems, including the arrester, are suitable for hydrogen and a pressure of 16 bar.
Due to the low ignition energy, there is a risk of fire and/or explosion when venting larger quantities (> 100 liters) of hydrogen.	Flaring is preferred; if flaring is not possible and ignition of the released hydrogen cloud can be ruled out, venting is permitted.	Ensure that venting and flaring systems, including the arrester, are suitable for hydrogen and a pressure of 16 bar.
Hearing damage caused by escaping or burning hydrogen.	Use hearing protection.	Possibly a different type of hearing protection.
Fire and/or explosion hazard.	Continuously measure both methane and hydrogen concentrations; do not use ignition sources on or in the vicinity of the workplace. Place 'No open fires' signs. Do not use ignition sources on or in the vicinity of the workplace. Except for hand tools, only ATEX-certified equipment may be present during gas-related work. This applies to electronic equipment (smartwatches, smartphones, tablets, etc.), electrical equipment (including brushless devices), and mechanical equipment (e.g., air-powered devices or combustion engines).	Spark-free tools are of even greater importance. Maintain greater safety distances.
Personal injury due to burns.	Use personal protection equipment.	Possible additional protection against fire.

In paragraph 10.4 the measures to reduce the risk of the hazards “uncontrolled release of hydrogen” and “fire and/or explosion hazard” are explained.

10.3 Suitability of measuring instruments and equipment

When carrying out maintenance and operation activities, it goes without saying that equipment suitable for the application is deployed. Given that the current maximum operating pressure in distribution grids is 8 bar, the suitability of the following equipment must be explicitly guaranteed when applying an operating pressure of 16 bar;

- Pressure gauges
- Drilling equipment
- Stopples
- Venting and flare equipment, including flame arrester.

Concentration meters will generally need to be protected against excessive pressure. This applies to a pressure of 8 bar as well as 16 bar.

10.4 Measures in case of uncontrolled hydrogen release and fire/explosion hazard

When increasing the pressure in the distribution grid from 8 bar to 16 bar, unexpected leak openings⁴ will result in a higher leakage rate. The HyDelta 3 study “Hydrogen Leaks and Control Measures” [53] concludes that approaching and repairing hydrogen leaks can be carried out safely. In that report, the safety distances are related to the leakage rate. For this reason, the findings from that report are also applicable to a hydrogen distribution grid operating at 16 bar.

Compared to natural gas, additional or modified measures are required to protect the technician and the surrounding. Maintaining wider safety distances for medium and large gas leaks is an important example of this. In 8 bar grids, depending on the cause of the leak, there will be medium or large gas leaks. In 16 bar grids, a leak may more quickly result in a large leak (see Appendix I).

For the sake of completeness, this chapter covers dealing with leaks in distribution grids at both higher and lower pressures. After all, grids with lower pressures may also be situated in the vicinity of 16 bar grids. The information included below is based on the HyDelta 3 study “Hydrogen leaks and control measures” [53] and partly taken from an article of the Dutch Gas grid Knowledge Centre, “Safety distances in the event of hydrogen leaks”. [54]

The measures mentioned below (correct distances, sectioning in combination with nitrogen purging, and some additional measures) are not all listed in the hydrogen VWIs (see Table 5).

Appropriate safety distances ensure acceptable risks.

Technicians, emergency responders, and bystanders must maintain a certain distance from the leak to ensure that the gas leak does not pose a danger to them. The potential dangers of a gas leak are:

- Heat radiation after ignition of the gas
- Flying debris or glass as a result of an explosion
- Pressure wave resulting from delayed ignition
- Suffocation by the gas due to the absence of oxygen⁵

⁴ Appendix I includes an explanation of the relationship between leakrate, the causes of leaks, and the method of initial detection of various gas leaks.

⁵ If work is carried out in accordance with the national Hydrogen Safety Instructions (the Dutch 'VIAG' for hydrogen), the risk of suffocation is not realistic. Working in accordance with these instructions means, for example, leaving the workplace at a gas concentration of 10% LEL. This concentration will never lead to suffocation.

Naturally, bystanders are not always aware of the dangers. Emergency responders must keep bystanders at the appropriate safety distance. The danger associated with a gas leak depends on the size of the flow rate and the location where the leak occurs (inside or outside a building).

For each of the above mentioned hazards, different safety distances are applicable. These are listed in Table 6. It should be noted that the ignition of a gas cloud must be prevented. This can be achieved by applying a safety distance corresponding to the distance to a gas cloud with a concentration of 99% LEL at the edges. However, for safety reasons, 10% LEL is used. At that distance, there is also no risk of suffocation, even though this distance is actually much smaller. A gas cloud can take on

LEL, LFL en onderste brandbaarheidsgrens

In dit rapport wordt voor de onderste brandbaarheidsgrens van een gas de afkorting LEL gebruikt. De afkorting LEL sluit aan bij de Nederlandse en Europese in gebruik zijnde normen (zie NEN 7244 en NEN-EN 1839). In deze normen wordt geen onderscheid gemaakt tussen LEL (lower explosion limit) en LFL (lower flammability limit).

Met LEL en LFL wordt de onderste brandbaarheidsgrens bedoeld. Beneden de onderste brandbaarheidsgrens is er onvoldoende brandstof aanwezig om een verbrandingsreactie in stand te houden. Boven de onderste brandbaarheidsgrens is een mengsel van gas en lucht wel te ontsteken. Voor waterstof is de onderste brandbaarheidsgrens 4 vol% waterstof in lucht, voor aardgas is deze waarde 5,8 vol%. Gasdetectieapparatuur (persoonlijk beschermingsmiddel) geeft een signalering bij het bereiken van 10% van de onderste brandbaarheidsgrens (het display toont 10% LEL).

various forms depending on the leakage rate, the location of the leak opening, the environment in which the gas is released, and the wind speed. In the event of a gas leak, a gas cloud will never have a homogeneous concentration. At the outlet, the gas concentration is always 100%; this concentration decreases towards the edges of the gas cloud.

Table 6: Safety distances at different leakage rates

Safety distances in meters for protection against various hazards [53]						
Type of leakage	Leakage rate (m ³ /hour)	Distance to gas cloud 10% LEL	Distance to gas cloud 100% LEL	Heat radiation max 3 kW/m ²	Flying debris/glass	Pressure resulting from delayed ignition in the open air
Small	< 0.05	no	no	no	no	no
Medium-sized	up to 50	approximately 16 m	approximately 3 m	approximately 3 m	50 to 70 m	10 m
Big	> 50	approximately 20 m	approximately 4 m	10 m	50 to 70 m	10 m

When selecting the appropriate distance to the gas leak, the greatest safety distance, as listed in Table 6, is the guiding principle. If leaking gas can enter a building, the distance is that of flying debris or glass; this is 50 to 70 meters. If leaking gas cannot enter a building, the safety distance is the distance to a gas cloud with a concentration of 10% LEL at the edge. At the corresponding safety distance (approximately 16 or 20 meters), no injury due to heat radiation or increased pressure is to be expected either.

A practical approach to maintaining a safe distance from the gas leak, based on the aforementioned report, is as follows;

- 1) Based on the report and, if applicable, on your own observations at the scene, determine whether the leak is small, medium, or large. The tables in Appendix I may be helpful in this regard. Important starting points;
 - A leak in a 16 bar line is always a major leak.
 - Excavation damage resulting in free gas outflow always involves a medium-sized or large leak.
 - An above-ground observable leak in a high-pressure distribution grid (always concerns a medium-sized or large leak)
 - If gas is detected in a building (smell), assume a medium or large leak.
- 2) If a small leak outside a building is expected, maintaining safety distances is of secondary importance. However, it is advisable to determine whether there is a measurable gas concentration in nearby buildings (for example, near the gas line entering the building). Be alert for any accumulation of gas in crawl spaces. If gas concentrations exceed 10% LEL, the premises must be evacuated.
- 3) In the event of a medium- or large leak that has **not** entered, or cannot enter, a building, maintain a safety distance of **at least 20 meters** and, perhaps even more importantly, a position upwind. At this distance, there is no danger due to heat or pressure should the gas ignite at a later time. If a concentration of 10% LEL is still measured at this distance, a greater distance must be chosen.
- 4) In the event of a medium- or large leak that **has** entered a building, or where it is likely that the leak will enter a building, maintain a safety distance of **at least 70 meters**. At this distance, there is no danger from heat, pressure waves, or flying debris and glass should the gas ignite at a later time. Ensure that the buildings in the immediate vicinity of the gas leak are evacuated.

By maintaining these distances, the risk of injury from fire, explosion, or flying debris is greatly reduced.

Sectioning in combination with nitrogen purging prevents flammable mixtures.

Prior to repairing a leak, the gas supply must be shut off at the appropriate safety distance. In high-pressure grids, this is done by closing section valves or by installing plugs. In the case of a large leak opening, the sectioned pipe may quickly become depressurized. If this is not the case, a flare system with a flame arrestor must be installed. Once the pipe has become depressurized, it must be dehydrogenated by purging with nitrogen. In the case of a large leak opening, this must be done by injecting nitrogen at both ends of the sectioned part. The hydrogen is then expelled from the pipe sections through the leak opening. The flow of purging is directed towards the leak.

In the case of a large leak opening, the soil may be saturated with hydrogen. Since the risks of digging in hydrogen-saturated soil are currently unknown, the purging period must be selected such that the gas concentration in the soil to be excavated is < 10% LEL.

In the case of a small leak, the injection of nitrogen on one side of the sectioned part is sufficient. On the other side of the sectioned part, a flare system with a flame arrestor must be installed to vent the hydrogen.

During the repair of the leak, air may enter the nitrogen-filled pipe. For this reason, the pipe will need to be flushed with nitrogen again after the repair is complete. Afterward, the pipe can be made commissioned with hydrogen.

Additional measures

In addition to applying the wider safety distances mentioned above and purging with nitrogen, there are further differences in the approach to approaching and repairing a gas leak. The additional measures for approaching and repairing a hydrogen leak (in 100 mbar, 8 bar, and 16 bar distribution grids) are:

1. A leak should be approached with a thermal imaging camera.
2. Gas detection equipment with H₂ and an O₂ sensors must be used.
3. Temporary repairs may not be carried out under gas pressure.
4. Mechanics will need to receive additional instructions.
5. Locating a leak using a drag mat method is possible up to 10% LEL (0.4% H₂).
6. Measure the gas concentration in nearby buildings.

The additional measures are explained below.

Use of a thermal imaging camera

If a hydrogen leak is ignited, the flame is not always visible. Whether the flame is visible depends on various factors. The flow rate and the location of the leak are determining factors. A leak with a large outflow into the ground will draw sand along with it. This contamination makes a resulting flame visible. In the case of a small leak in an above-ground pipe, there will be little dirt present in the gas flow. Due to limited heat generation, such a flame may not always be visible. To prevent injury from fire, the use of a thermal imaging camera is advisable when responding to every report of a gas leak.

Gas detection equipment

It goes without saying that a technician performing work on a hydrogen distribution grid is equipped with a gas detector fitted with an H₂ sensor. In addition, the O₂ concentration must also be continuously measured via the gas detector (personal protection equipment). When purging the hydrogen pipeline with nitrogen, a large amount of nitrogen can be released. This can lead to suffocation in an working pit, for example. In addition to measuring H₂ and O₂ via personal protective equipment, equipment containing H₂ and O₂ sensors will also need to be used for purging operations.

Temporary repairs not under gas pressure

In natural gas distribution grids, temporary repairs under gas pressure are permitted (Dutch VWI G-37). This is not the case when using hydrogen. This is due to the greater risks associated with a hydrogen leak compared to natural gas.

Additional instructions for technicians

Working on a hydrogen distribution grid requires a different approach than working with natural gas. In particular, the wider flammability limits of hydrogen and the difference in the impact of an unexpected ignition result in greater risks. If a technician is using the standard natural gas working methods on a hydrogen distribution grid, the likelihood of incidents and the potential effects would be greater. The number of hydrogen distribution grids will remain limited, particularly in the coming years. As a result, technicians will be able to gain less practical experience. In addition to providing initial supplementary work instructions, it is therefore necessary to maintain knowledge through refresher training.

Locating a leak

Leaks in main and service lines can be detected using above-ground leak detection (drag mat or bell jar). If an indication of a leak follows from this above-ground leak detection (in accordance with Dutch NEN 7249), the leak must be repaired. Specifically locating hydrogen leaks can still be safely performed up to gas concentrations < 10% LEL. However, when detecting smaller above-ground leaks

(<5 l/h), it is logical that this 10% LEL value will be exceeded in practice if a detector is held close to a leak. With such small leaks (a factor of 10 smaller than 0.05 m³ / h), no unsafe situation is to be expected for the grid operator's technician. The gas supply to this leak must, of course, be stopped.

Measuring gas concentrations in nearby buildings

When repairing a gas leak, the gas supply will first be shut off. If the leaking gas could spread to a building, it must be established that the gas concentration in that building is < 10% LEL. Gas concentration measurements in nearby buildings must also be performed. If gas concentrations exceed 10% LEL, ventilation must be carried out first. If the concentration remains higher than 10% LEL, the building in question must be evacuated.

References

- [1] R. Octaviano, H. Blokland and R. v. d. Linden, "HyDelta 2 WP8 – Analysing digitalization in the network management. D8.1 – State of the art technologies in the current gas grid. D8.2 – Define the gap with the future hydrogen grid," HyDelta, 2022.
- [2] R. Octaviano, D. Palochis, J. Poort and H. Blokland, "HyDelta 2 WP8 – Analysing digitalization in the network management. D8.3 – Simulation results for the selected use cases. D8.4 – Final Report.," HyDelta, 2023.
- [3] F. Brissaud, "Predictive maintenance to prevent drifts. Applied to gas pressure reduction and delivery stations.," in *IGRC*, 2024.
- [4] J. L. Abreu, V. B. Casteli and M. Y. do Nascimento, "Utilization of Machine Learning for Prediction of Natural Gas Asset Damages Resulting from Third Party Underground Interventions," in *IGRC*, 2024.
- [5] Marcogaz, "Hydrogen gas in existing natural gas pipelines and cathodic protection; 2019; A.H.M. Krom; VA 19.0166.," *TF_H2-339*, 2019.
- [6] The American Society of Mechanical Engineers, "ASME B31.12 Hydrogen Piping and Pipelines," 2023.
- [7] European Industrial Gases Association, "Hydrogen Pipeline Systems," *IGC Doc 121/14*, 2014.
- [8] Pipeline Research Council International, "Emerging fuels – Hydrogen SOTA, Gap Analysis, Future Project Roadmap," *PR-720-20603-R01*.
- [9] Marcogaz, "Overview of test results & regulatory limits for hydrogen admission into existing natural gas infrastructure & end use (so called 'Marcogaz Infographic')," *TF_H2-427*, 2019.
- [10] Pipeline Research Council International, "Hydrogen/Natural Gas Blends and Pipeline Integrity," *PR744-22113-E01E*, 2022.
- [11] "IOPscience," [Online]. Available: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/ad6463>. [Accessed januari 2026].
- [12] "IEA," [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-methane-tracker-2025/understanding-methane-emissions>. [Accessed januari 2026].
- [13] "Nature," [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s43247-023-00857-8>. [Accessed januari 2026].
- [14] "Agupubs," [Online]. Available: <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1029/1999JD900788>. [Accessed januari 2026].
- [15] "Climate.mit.edu," [Online]. Available: <https://climate.mit.edu/ask-mit/why-do-we-blame-climate-change-carbon-dioxide-when-water-vapor-much-more-common-greenhouse>. [Accessed januari 2026].

- [16] "ScienceDaily," [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2024/11/241105114155.htm>. [Accessed januari 2026].
- [17] N. Vermeldfoort, "HyDelta 1; D1F.1 Testing valves in the transmission grid (>16 bar).," [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/6541814>.
- [18] NEN 1059, *Gasdrukregel- en meetstations voor transport en distributie*, NEN, 2019.
- [19] Kiwa Technology, "HyDelta D1B.4 Stoftransport met waterstof/aardgas ten behoeve van filters," 2022.
- [20] Kiwa Technology, "Gasdrukregelstation voor waterstof - GT-200308," 2021.
- [21] S. v. Woudenberg, "HyDelta: D1B.1 Operation of gas stations with spring loaded regulators with hydrogen," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469611>.
- [22] N. Zafer, "Stability of gas pressure regulators," *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, 2008.
- [23] S. Sharma, "Health Monitoring of PRS in Gas Distribution Networks using mathematical models," *Energies*, 2022.
- [24] Kiwa Technology, "HyDelta D1C.2, dichtheid van distributieleidingen," 2021.
- [25] NEN 7244-1, *Gasvoorzieningsystemen - Leidingen voor maximale bedrijfsdruk tot en met 16 bar - Deel 1: Nederlandse editie op basis van NEN-EN 12007-1 - Algemene functionele eisen*, NEN, 2014.
- [26] S. van Woudenberg, M. van der Laan, "HyDelta 2.0 - D6B.1A/ D6B.1B – Inventarisatie, modellering en experimenten met betrekking tot ventilatie in verschillende typen gasdrukregelstations in het distributie (lagedruk)net in Nederland met aardgas en waterstof," New Energy Coalition - TKI2022 - HyDelta, 2023.
- [27] van Woudenberg, S., Sweers, T., "Hydelta 3.0 - WP5e Improved ventilation in gas stations," 2024.
- [28] R. Crewe, M. Johnson, D. Allason, "Hy4heat WP7 Ignition potential testing with hydrogen and methane," Hy4heat/ DNV, 2020.
- [29] Hydelta 3 D1A.2, "Strategies/Scenarios on how to deliver hydrogen purity in distribution networks," 2024.
- [30] KIWA, "Toekomstbestendige gasdistributienetten," Netbeheer Nederland, 2018.
- [31] KIWA, "Permeatie van waterstof," Netbeheer Nederland, 2022.
- [32] Hydelta 1 D1C.3, "The influence of the existing natural gas distribution networks on the purity of hydrogen," 2022.
- [33] Gasunie, "H2 in an existing natural gas pipeline," Calgary, 2020.
- [34] Hydelta 1 D2.5, "Advice on odorant choice," 2022.

- [35] A. Król, "Hydrogen Purification Technologies in the Context of Its Utilization," [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/17/15/3794>. [Accessed januari 2026].
- [36] HyDelta 3 D1A.1, "Overview of basic elements for hydrogen purity standards," 2024.
- [37] F. Cagnon, A. Louvat and V. Vasseur, "The gas smell; a study on the public perception of gas," in *IGRC conference*, 2011.
- [38] Hydeltta 1 D2.4, "The risk of not odourising hydrogen," 2022.
- [39] "Shimmer," [Online]. Available: <https://shimmerproject.eu/>. [Accessed januari 2026].
- [40] Hydeltta 3 D4B.2, "Optimal sensor placement strategies for monitoring the dynamic pressure of gas networks," 2024.
- [41] "Gasunie Hydrogen Network Netherlands," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gasunie.nl/en/projects/hydrogen-network-netherlands>. [Accessed januari 2026].
- [42] DBI, DNV, LBST, Trinomics, "Study on hydrogen quality in dedicated infrastructure and standardisation," European Commission, 2025.
- [43] P. v. Wesenbeeck, "Hydrogen and carbon dioxide specifications for pipeline transport," in *VSL Themadag 2025*, Delft, 2025.
- [44] DNV, KIWA, "A follow-up study into the hydrogen quality requirements," Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy (EZK), 2023.
- [45] K. Letsios, K. Letsios, N. D. Charisou, G. S. Skodras, M. A. Goula and S. L. Douvartzides, "Hydrogen Compression Choices for Tomorrow's Refueling Stations: Review of Recent Advances and Selection Guide," *Hydrogen*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 25, 2026.
- [46] P. Engineering, "Primer on compressed air filtration," *Plant Engineering*, 1 June 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://www.plantengineering.com/primer-on-compressed-air-filtration/>. [Accessed 12 February 2026].
- [47] A. Król, M. Gajec, J. Holewa-Rataj, E. Kukulska-Zajac and M. Rataj, "Hydrogen Purification Technologies in the Context of Its Utilization," *Energies*, vol. 17, no. 15, p. 3794, 2024.
- [48] B. Renewables, "Bright Renewables biogas upgrading membrane," Bright Renewables, [Online]. Available: <https://www.bright-renewables.com/technology/biogas-upgrading-membrane/>. [Accessed 11 February 2026].
- [49] S. H. Chang and M. F. Rajuli, "An overview of pure hydrogen production via electrolysis and hydrolysis," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 84, pp. 521-538, 2024.
- [50] Enexis, *Richtlijn Groen Gas invoeding op gasnet*, Gza-018.K, 2018.
- [51] Enexis, *Werkinstructie voor de afhandeling storingen van off-spec gas vanuit GTS of Groen Gas invoeders*, Gzc-0007.I, 2021.
- [52] Netbeheer Nederland, "Richtlijnen beheersprotocol groengas invoedingen," 2016.

- [53] S. Lueb, S. Woudenberg and M. Bos, "HyDelta WPB5 - Waterstoflekkages en beheersmaatregelen," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/15023952>.
- [54] S. Lueb, "Kenniscentrum Gasnetbeheer - Veiligheidsafstanden bij waterstoflekkages," 2025. [Online].
- [55] G. Gaikhorst, O van Uchelen, "Ventilatie in kaststations - VEG gasinstituut," *GAS*, pp. 433 - 441, November 1971.
- [56] NEN-EN-1127, *Plaatsen waar explosiegevaar kan heersen - Explosiepreventie en- bescherming - deel 1: grondbeginselen en methodologie*, 2019.
- [57] NPR-7910-1, "NPR7910-1 - Classification of hazardous areas with respect to explosion hazard - Part 1: Gas explosion hazard, based on NEN-EN-IEC 60079-10-1:2015," NEN, 2021.
- [58] N. Vermeltfoort, M. van der Laan, "Concentratie metingen in ventilatieopeningen van districtregelstations," Kiwa Technology BV, 2022.
- [59] N. Vermeltfoort, M. van der Laan, "GT-220349 HI FLOW Sampler metingen bij gasstations," Kiwa Technology, 2022.
- [60] Charlotte Große, Melanie Eyßer, Stefanie Lehmann, Jenny Sammüller, Marco Behnke, Klaus Peters, "Research Project Methane Emission DSO Has Been Completed," *Energy, Wasser-praxis*, Vols. 5 - 2022, pp. 1 - 8, 2022.
- [61] NEN-EN-IEC60079-10-1, "Explosive atmospheres - Part 10-1: Classification of areas - explosive gas atmospheres (IEC-60079-10-1:2020, IDT)," Nederlandse norm, 2021.
- [62] S. van Woudenberg, "HyDelta 1.0 - WP1B Gasstations - Ventilatie," New Energy Coalition - TKI2020 - HyDelta, 2022.
- [63] Esders, "<https://www.esders.nl/2021/06/effecten-van-toevoeging-van-waterstof-aan-aardgas-op-de-explosiebeveiliging-van-gasmeet-en-gaswaarschuwingsapparatuur/>," Esders, 2021. [Online]. [Accessed 2025].

I. Distinction of leaks and method of initial detection

In report [53] a classification has been made into three types of leaks based on the leakage volume. This distinction yields three types of leaks: small (<0.05 m³/hour), medium (up to 50 m³/hour), or large (> 50 m³/hour). The leak opening and the pressure in the gas pipeline determine the leakage rate. The resulting leak opening often depends on the cause of the leakage. The expected leakage rate for a specific cause and pressure in the pipeline is shown below. Based on this, it can be concluded, for example, that excavation damage (resulting in free gas outflow) will usually involve a medium or large leak, and that an above-ground leak observable (due to the mentioned causes) in a high-pressure grid (> 200 mbar) always concerns a medium or large leak.

Leakage rate dependent on pipe pressure and the cause of the leakage									
Mains pressure	16 bar			8 or 4 bar			100 mbar		
Leakage rate	small	medium	large	small	medium	large	small	medium	large
Cause of leakage									
Corrosion/aging	-	V	V	-	V	V	V	V	-
Excavation damage	-	-	V	-	-	V	-	V	V
Construction defects	-	V	V	-	V	-	V	V	-
Functioning of the soil*	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	-	-	V
Point load (at PE)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	V	-	V	V	-
Power cable overload**	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	-	-	V
- = mentioned cause cannot lead to this type V = mentioned cause can lead to this type of leak N/A = the mentioned cause is not applicable at this grid pressure *Soil movement; leaks occur particularly at non-tensile connections, which are not present in the high-pressure grid. **Power cable overload; no known situations where a synthetic high-pressure pipe has started leaking as a result of an overloaded power cable.									

Leaks in a hydrogen distribution grid can be detected in various ways (just as in a natural gas distribution grid). The table below shows that the method of detection does not provide direct insight into the extent of the leak. In case of doubt regarding the classification by type and consequently the choice of safety distances, the largest leak type should be used as the basis. The table below assumes that the hydrogen is odorized.

Method for detecting gas leaks in a distribution grid		
Type of leak	Usual method of initial detection of unignited hydrogen	
	Exterior	Indoors
Small (<0.05 m ³ /hour)	drag mat	smell, pressure drop test
Medium (up to 50 m ³ /hour)	drag mat, smell, grass discoloration, noise, power outage	smell
Large (> 50 m ³ /hour)	drag mat, smell, grass discoloration, noise, power outage, spraying soil	smell

Small gas leaks in a gas station can also be detected using a gas detector (sniffer) or leak detection spray. Gas leaks in a gas station are typically not noticed by bystanders, but during scheduled inspections.

II. An explanation of the ATEX regulations - general

What is the current standard?

In HyDelta 2, extensive research was conducted into the ventilation of gas station cabinets in the event of a leak [26]. The report outlines which laws and regulations apply and how they are applied to gas distribution. In short, this boils down to the following:

Under the European ATEX 153 directive, employers are legally required to indicate ATEX zoning in areas where explosive substances are present. The risk is determined based on a risk inventory and evaluation. This establishes the link with the ATEX 114 directive. ATEX 114-approved equipment is subdivided into categories, which indicate in which zones this equipment may be used so that it cannot ignite an explosive atmosphere.

The directive applies to devices, components, and safety systems used in potentially hazardous areas (in our case, gas distribution systems).

In case of the distribution of hydrogen, the approach is that safety must be at least comparable to that of natural gas. Consequently, (the cabinet of) a hydrogen gas station must also be at least as safe as (the cabinet of) a natural gas station. To achieve this, care must be taken to ensure that the public domain can be designated as a “Non-Hazardous Area (NGG)”. For natural gas, the area within the cabinet of a gas station, as applied to RNBS, is often qualified as an ATEX Zone 2, and the “Non-Hazardous Area” begins immediately outside the cabinet if it complies with NEN 1059. For this reason, fencing is normally not installed around a natural gas distribution station. Ideally, the same should apply to hydrogen stations. A cabinet (or: the cabinet including a fenced area of ground surface) must be capable of being classified as an ATEX Zone 2; however, this will depend on the preconditions set during the situation analysis that determines the assignment of a zoning classification.

NEN:1059, 2019 states that if the ventilation rate exceeds 5 times per hour, ATEX Zone 2 can be applied inside the cabinet. In that case, no zoning applies outside the cabinet is considered to be mandatory. In the event of a minor leak, sufficient ventilation should be present to effectively vent off the escaping gas.

The basis for this requirement was established and presented in a GAS article [55]. Here, it was determined via a set of differential equations that a mutual relationship can be established between the volume of the enclosure, the ventilation rate, and the leakage rate. Furthermore, by means of experiments, the equilibrium concentration at a defined leakage was determined for various field configurations.

The basis of the above standardization lies in declaring the installation technically leak-tight in accordance with NEN-EN 1127 Annex B (B.3 – “Enhanced tightness”) [56] or NPR-7910-1 (2021) [57]. However, because very small leaks are not immediately detected, it is advisable to classify the interior of the enclosure as ATEX zone 2, where the zone does not extend outside the enclosure. This way, zoning is not required outside the enclosure.

Research [58, 59] shows that regular leaks are small and are not always noticed by the surroundings. However, a realistic leak opening for a regular leak is not explicitly mentioned in references. Based on recent research, it has been established that such a leak rarely exceeds 40 liters per hour [59, 60]. At such leakage rates, it is unlikely that odorized gas will be noticed by a passer-by because dilution occurs by wind and the odor threshold is only reached close to the leak.

The same report explains how a zone determination can be made based on NPR7910 [57] and NEN-EN-IEC-60079-10-1 [61].

What is known from previous research

During the various phases of Hydelta (parts 1, 2 and 3), extensive research was conducted into the role of ventilation in cabinets and cabinet stations for both natural gas and hydrogen [26] [62] [27]. During these studies, there was substantial discussion regarding the difference between outflow during an emergency and a minor leak during normal operation. In both cases, ATEX zoning is applied as a mitigating measure.

Experiments have established that with the currently applied ventilation in two tested enclosures (a flap cabinet (0.5 m³) and a cabinet station (4 m³)), sufficient ventilation is provided for a leakage of 40 l/h natural gas (or equivalent, 125 l/h hydrogen) to avoid exceeding the lower flammability limit. Increasing the ventilation for hydrogen installations is recommended [27] and leads to lower equilibrium concentrations within the cabinet.

What changes when hydrogen is used instead of natural gas?

When switching from natural gas to hydrogen, legislation and regulations regarding explosion safety must be complied with. These requirements are generally stricter than those for natural gas due to the wider flammability limits and the low minimum ignition energy (MIE) of hydrogen.

Every device intended for use in a potentially explosive atmosphere (in accordance with the ATEX Directive and that is also certified) bears its own marking in the form of a clearly visible label on the device. This label contains coded information regarding explosion protection classifications. Such a label is shown in the figure below.

Figure 8; example of an Ex marking for a device

The certification of components placed in an explosion-proof environment is normally classified according to the logic of gas families. Gases and gas mixtures are subdivided into three groups.

Typically, this concerns gas groups IIA and IIB, which account for approximately 98% of the market wide available applications. This involves the following subdivision, where the Roman numerals I, II, and III represent for I mine gas and/or town gas, II represents many other gases, and III represents

substances (flour, sugar, wood), respectively. Naturally, components in gas groups I and II are focused on gases;

- **IIA** : This category includes methane, ethane and propane, among others
- **IIB** : This category includes ethylene, carbon monoxide, and gas mixtures such as town gas, which may contain up to 60% v/v hydrogen
- **IIC** : This category includes hydrogen (100%) and acetylene

The rules applicable to a higher explosion group are stricter than those for a lower explosion group. These rules therefore also apply to the lower group and are consequently supplemented with additional requirements.

Electrical equipment placed in a zone can be subdivided based on the nature of the potentially explosive atmosphere for which it is intended. The subdivision is based on the gap width (or Maximum Experimental Safe Gap (MESG) for flame-retardant enclosures and the minimum ignition energy (MIE). The figure below graphically illustrates how hydrogen content influences the selection of the gas family used. With the distribution of 100% hydrogen, gas group IIC must be adhered to for all explosion-proof equipment.

Figure 9; the gap width (MESG) as a function of the amount of hydrogen (in vol%) in natural gas (left) and the amount of hydrogen in methane (right) [63]

The gap width (MESG) is therefore a standardized measure of how easily a gas flame can pass through a narrow opening bounded by heat-absorbing metal. This gap width can be used to classify flammable gases for the design and/or selection of electrical equipment in potentially hazardous environments.

The graph shows that equipment located in an ATEX-classified zone and in direct contact with a mixture (of natural gas and hydrogen) belongs to Zone IIA or IIB. Specific equipment used for 100% v/v hydrogen qualify under Zone IIC.

The ignition of a combustible mixture is always an interaction between the flammability limits, the minimum ignition energy of the combustible mixture (fuel-to-air ratio), and the ignition source. This ignition source must contain (and be able to release) more energy than the minimum ignition energy to be successful as an ignition source. The MIE can be caused in various ways (flame, hot surface, shock spark), whereby electrical equipment can also be a potential ignition source. In the case of electrical equipment, the Minimum Ignition Current (MIC) is also taken into account for intrinsically safe electrical equipment, as required in the specific European standards.

When classifying gas mixtures into the above-mentioned explosion groups, a direct relationship can be established between the gap width and the minimum ignition energy (MIE or MIC). There is a

functional relationship between the two quantities, allowing them to be assessed together and to show their interlinking property as ignition source [63].

This information is compiled in the table below, which can also be partly traced back to ISO/IEC 80079-20-1 .

Explosiegroep	Standaard spleetbreedte mm	Minimale ontstekingsenergie (geschatte waarde) mJ
II A	> 0,90	> 0,20
II B	0,50 - 0,90	0,05 - 0,20
II C	< 0,50	< 0,05

When using a different gas, the above assessment will have to be made.

Components with the EX marking for natural gas must be checked for specific logo abbreviations. A component used in an explosive environment is always certified for a specific environment and is labeled accordingly.

When switching from natural gas to hydrogen (or a mixture of natural gas and hydrogen), some of these label areas on the EX marking of an appliance may be affected. The label in Figure 8 is a general example of an equipment label. It contains three marked areas (red circles) that require extra attention in this specific case. The first red-marked circle concerns the protection mode (nu db eb), which is a guideline for electrical equipment.

[The IEC60079 series provides a lot of information.](#)

The IEC 60079 series can be used for the analysis of new and existing systems. IEC 60079-10-1 describes the classification of areas where potentially hazardous, flammable gases or vapors may occur, so that the appropriate electrical equipment can be selected for those environments. The standard establishes criteria for determining the size and shape of hazardous zones (such as Zone 0, 1, and 2) and provides guidelines to reduce the risk of ignition.

Within the IEC60079 series, specific sub-standards are available regarding how to handle repurposing. Generally, the following standards are consulted when the gas in the installation is changed. The table below lists the minimum consultations that must be performed when an installation is designated for repurposing;

Table 7; overview of standards from the IEC 60079 series that may apply to repurposing

Standard	Title / Subject	What does this standard regulate?	Application for gas changes / reassessment?
IEC 60079-0	General requirements for Ex equipment	Basic standard: construction requirements, markings, temperature limits, IP protection, mechanical strength and test methods	Check if equipment is suitable for gas group and temperature class
ISO/IEC 80079-20-1*	Gas and vapor properties	Physical properties such as explosion limits, MIE, gas groups and temperature classes	Determine which gas group and T-class apply to the new gas
IEC 60079-10-1	Zone classification (gas)	Classification of explosion-hazardous zones based on gas sources, ventilation, and scenarios	New zone classification for different process gas or composition
IEC 60079-14	Design and installation of Ex installations	Selection and installation of explosion-proof equipment, cables, Ex markings, temperature classes, and assembly methods	Choice/ Installation inspection of suitable equipment for the new gas
IEC 60079-17	Inspection and maintenance	Inspection and maintenance of electrical installations	Selection/installation check of suitable equipment for various protection types such as 'Ex d', 'Ex e', 'Ex n', 'Ex t' and 'Ex pd'

*) ISO/IEC80079-20-1 is harmonised and derives from IEC60079-20-1 (2019)

The order of the consultations is important to reach the correct conclusions. First, the future application of explosion safety according to the IEC 60079 series must be examined at the installation level; this is followed by analyses of the type of gas and the impact of the gas in question on the zoning requirements, followed by the selection of the appropriate components and protection systems.

Does the check change when only the system pressure is changed?

Even when the decision is made to switch a gas pressure regulating system to hydrogen and set it to 16 bar instead of 8 bar, a thorough analysis must be carried out regarding structural safety, suitability, and explosion safety. In addition, the question arises whether the installation is technically suitable for this conversion.

In this case, the same sequence of checks can be carried out as when a plan for repurposing is formulated.

Table 8; overview of standards from the IEC 60079 series that may apply to pressure-based repurposing

Standard	Mandatory revision?	Scope of application
IEC 60079-0	Yes	Reassess T-class, marking & strength
ISO/ IEC 80079-20-1	Indirectly*	Reapply gas data
IEC 60079-10-1	Yes	Zone larger/different due to higher leakage rates
IEC 60079-14	Yes	Re-evaluate installation & selection
IEC 60079-17	Yes	Detailed inspection after modification
IEC 60079-1	If Ex d	Mechanical and explosion pressure requirements
IEC 60079-7	If Ex e	Thermal limits
IEC 60079-2	If Ex p	Overpressure settings

Also here, the order of consultations is important to reach the correct conclusions. The process is again carried out from the installation level to the application of the gas (at a different pressure) to the consequences for zoning, component selection, and protection systems. In the event that an installation contains electrical components, additional parts of the IEC 60079 series will need to be consulted.

Why does Part 19 of IEC 60079 not need to be applied?

In the IEC-60079 series of standards, a specific part is also available regarding the repair, overhaul, and return of explosion-proof equipment. This concerns Part 19. This standard is not a standard for the inspection or assessment of installations. IEC 60079-19 deals exclusively with the repair, overhaul, and return of explosion-proof equipment and is a standard for workshops that repair Ex equipment, not for installation owners or inspection bodies. Therefore, it is not applied to;

- Modification of the process gas
- Reassessment of an installation
- Reclassifying zones
- Check if equipment is suitable for a different gas

The standard may also not be used to reassess the suitability of equipment.

This standard explains how a damaged component should be repaired without compromising explosion safety, but it does not provide guidance on gas groups applicability and T-classes suitable for newly applied gases, design selection, installation requirements, risk analysis, temperature limits, and zoning. The standards in Table 7 intended for this purpose.

The focus is primarily on the inspection and maintenance of installations and explosion safety.

IEC 60079-17 describes the requirements for the inspection and maintenance of electrical installations in explosive atmospheres, with the aim of ensuring safety and proper operation throughout their entire service life. The standard explains that inspections must be carried out by competent and trained personnel familiar with explosion safety principles and the relevant protection methods. The content of the standard supplements IEC 60364-6.

Three inspection levels are distinguished in IEC 60079-17—visual, thorough and detailed—which vary in thoroughness and are selected based on the risk profile of the area, the condition of the installation, and the nature of the equipment. During inspections, the overall condition of the installation is assessed, including damage, corrosion, sagging of connections, loose connections, missing or damaged seals, correct markings, the condition of cabinets, nuts and washers, and the maintenance of the prescribed protection method.

Attention to cabling, strain relief, and equipotential bonding is also essential to prevent the occurrence of potentially dangerous ignition sources. The frequency of inspections is determined by factors such as zone classification, environmental influences, and previous inspection results; installations in more severe conditions must be checked more frequently.

The standard emphasizes that repairs and replacements must be carried out in accordance with the original explosion safety specifications and that work must be carefully documented, including findings and any corrective measures. This ensures that the installation remains demonstrably compliant with safety requirements and that the risk of ignition by electrical equipment is minimized.

IEC 60079-17 deliberately does not provide fixed, universal inspection intervals for the three inspection levels (visual, thorough and detailed). The standard emphasizes that inspection frequencies must be determined on a risk-based manner and depend on factors such as the zone classification, environmental influences, equipment type, operating conditions, and previous inspection results.

The list below indicates how the standard applies this principle in practice;

- Visual inspection
This inspection is generally performed most frequently, as it quickly detects clearly visible defects. In environments with more contamination, vibrations, or susceptibility to damage, this interval may be chosen shorter.
In practice : varying from a few months to annually, depending on anticipated risk.
- Thorough inspection
is performed less frequently than the visual inspection, as it requires more time and access. The interval is usually longer than that of the visual inspection, but is still periodic.
In practice : often annually to every several years, depending on installation condition and environment.
- Detailed inspection
This is the most intensive and may also include opening Ex equipment (provided it is safe). The standard prescribes that a detailed inspection is always performed upon initial commissioning, after which the subsequent interval depends on the condition of the installation and previous findings.
In practice : often every few years, sometimes longer in stable, clean environments.

IEC 60079-17 does not itself determine the exact inspection intervals, but requires the user to establish a tailored inspection strategy. A more severe zone (such as zone 0 or 1), aggressive environments, or poor historical results lead to shorter inspection intervals; for stable, clean, and well-maintained installations, longer intervals may be applied. The frequency must always be justified and documented.

ATEX-related conclusions

When a new or existing station is converted to hydrogen, multiple actions are necessary;

- First of all, consulting the IEC 60079 series of standards with an analysis of the relevant standards
- An existing natural gas station that is converted to hydrogen must once again comply with ATEX
- In many cases, the zoning will not change, because the secondary hazard source as defined in IEC-60079-10-1 still applies
- Components placed in the applied zone must be suitable for that purpose
- Natural gas and hydrogen belong to different gas families (Figure 8); components with an ATEX label must be suitable to be installed in the applied zone
- Equipment for hydrogen must be specifically classified for the IIC gas group, to which hydrogen belongs. This classification is carried out based on the MIE or the MIC. In the event that electrical equipment is placed in a zone, the maximum gap width (also known as the MESG) is used
- In addition, improved safety measures such as intrinsic safety or explosion-proof designs (Ex d, Ex eb) can be used to prevent ignition. Directly related to the much lower MIE is the change regarding potential ignition sources. In this case, replacement or re-inspection will be required
- Depending on the complexity of a gas pressure regulating system (standalone PRS or larger city gate station), the modifications may involve more than just the gas family
- Inspection and maintenance of electrical installations in explosive atmospheres must be carried out to ensure explosion safety throughout their entire lifespan. Inspections must be performed by competent and trained personnel familiar with explosion safety principles and the relevant protection methods
- IEC 60079-17 deliberately does not provide fixed, universal inspection intervals for the three inspection levels (visual, thorough and detailed). The standard emphasizes that inspection frequencies must be determined on a risk-based manner and depend on factors such as the applied zone classification, environmental influences, equipment type, operating conditions, and previous inspection results
- Previous HyDelta research has shown that applying increased ventilation in the cabinets of a hydrogen PRS is advisable due to the different behavior of hydrogen (HyDelta 2 and 3). This approach was also chosen in the hydrogen pilot projects (Lochem, Wagenborgen). However, when leakage is defined as a secondary hazard source, applying increased ventilation is not mandatory provided the correct zone is applied, but hydrogen can be vented more effectively in the event of a leak
- When a gas pressure regulating station is used for a higher pressure (16 bar instead of 8 bar), largely the same considerations will have to be made regarding explosion safety, the application of laws and regulations, and the application of IEC-60079

III. Overview of IEC 60079

Standard	Brief description of the content
<p>IEC 60079-0</p>	<p>IEC 60079-0 describes the general basic requirements for equipment and components used in explosive atmospheres (Ex zones). This standard forms the foundation for all other parts of the IEC 60079 series and establishes the basic safety standards that all explosion-proof equipment must meet before additional specific protection methods (such as Ex d, Ex e, Ex i) can be applied.</p> <p>Main content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scope of application: electrical and non-electrical equipment capable of operating in environments containing explosive gases, vapors, or dust. • Construction and design requirements: materials, cabinets, temperature management, ignition sources, mechanical strength and protection against external influences. • Temperature classes: rules for maximum surface temperatures to prevent ignition of explosive mixtures. • Markings: mandatory Ex markings, categories, protection modes and certification data on the device. • Tests: general test methods (mechanical, electrical, thermal, and environmental tests) that demonstrate that equipment is safe. • Documentation & Quality: requirements for technical documentation, traceability, and quality assurance by the manufacturer.
<p>IEC 80079-20-1</p>	<p>IEC 80079-20-1 describes the properties of gases and vapors relevant to the design and certification of explosion-proof equipment.</p> <p>The standard helps manufacturers, designers, and specialists to correctly classify substances according to their ignition and explosion characteristics. In short, IEC 80079-20-1 provides the fundamental material properties of gases and vapors required to correctly assess explosive atmospheres and select suitable Ex material.</p> <p>Main content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gas and vapor classification: classification of substances into explosive groups (IIA, IIB, IIC) based on their ignition properties. • Temperature classes: assignment of substances to temperature classes (T1–T6) depending on their minimum ignition temperature. • Material data: reference values for, among others <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ minimum ignition energy (MIE) ○ lower and upper flammability limits ○ relative density • Test methods: procedures to determine the stated material properties safely and reproducibly. • Use within the Ex design: data are used to align equipment, safeguards, and zone classifications with the properties of the substances present.
<p>IEC 60079-10-1</p>	<p>IEC 60079-10-1 provides guidelines for classifying areas where explosive gas atmospheres may occur. The goal is to determine the appropriate Ex zones in order to select suitable equipment and safety measures. In short, IEC 60079-10-1 offers a structured method for identifying and delineating zones with explosive gas atmospheres, so that appropriate explosion-proof equipment and measures can be applied.</p>

	<p>Main content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zone classification: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Zone 0: continuous or prolonged presence of an explosive gas atmosphere. ○ Zone 1: likely to occur during normal operation. ○ Zone 2: normally not present; if it occurs, then only briefly. • Analysis of ignition sources: assessment of leak sources, process conditions, ventilation, and potential spread of gases. • Ventilation assessment: guidelines for natural and mechanical ventilation to determine how quickly a gas cloud is diluted, which affects the zone size. • Factors influencing zone dimensions: leak size, gas or vapor class, temperature, installation conditions, and building characteristics. • Documentation: requirements for reporting assumptions, calculations, hazard sources, and final zone classification.
<p>IEC 60079-14</p>	<p>IEC 60079-14 describes the requirements for the design, selection, installation, and commissioning of electrical installations in explosive atmospheres (Ex zones). This standard is primarily used by manufacturers, designers, installers, and inspectors. In short, IEC 60079-14 provides practical guidance for the safe design and installation of electrical equipment in explosive atmospheres, so that ignition risks are minimized.</p> <p>Main content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design principles: Guidelines for a safe electrical installation based on zone classification, ambient temperatures, and the properties of the substances present. • Equipment selection: Equipment must be suitable for the relevant Ex zone, gas or dust group, and temperature class. The correct protection method (e.g., Ex d, Ex e, Ex i) must also be selected. • Installation requirements: Specifications for the correct mounting of cables, glands, conduits, cabinets, and connections. Special attention is also paid to seals, mechanical protection, and corrosion resistance. • Cabling and connections: Regulations for cable types, strain relief, cable entries, and the prevention of sparking at connection points. • Earthing and potential equalization: Measures to avoid static electricity and dangerous potential differences. • Commissioning and inspection: Requirements for initial check, test procedures, and documentation before an installation is put into operation.

IEC 60079-17

IEC 60079-17 contains the requirements and guidelines for the inspection and maintenance of electrical installations in explosive atmospheres (Ex zones). The goal is to ensure that installations continue to function safely throughout their entire lifespan. In short, IEC 60079-17 provides practical guidance for the safe inspection and maintenance of Ex installations, ensuring continued explosion safety.

Main content:

- **Inspection types:**
 - Visual inspection: detects visible defects without tools.
 - Close inspection: look more closely, sometimes with simple tools.
 - Detailed inspection: thorough check, including opening enclosures if safe.
- **Inspection frequency:**
Depending on zone, environmental conditions, equipment type, and historical reliability. High-risk areas require check-ups more frequently.
- **Inspection criteria:**
Checks for damage, corrosion, incorrect assembly, loose connections, seals, markings, cables and glands, correct protection methods, and condition of cabinets.
- **Maintenance:**
Repair and replacement procedures must comply with the original Ex specifications. Only authorized and trained personnel may perform repairs.
- **Documentation and registration:**
Inspections and maintenance must be recorded fully and systematically, including observed deviations and corrective measures.
- **Staff competence:**
Staff must have demonstrable knowledge and skills in explosion safety and the relevant standards.

IV. Overview of all parts of the IEC 60079 series (explosion safety)

Part	Title / Subject	Type (standard, TS or TR)
60079-0	General requirements	Standard
60079-1	Flame-proof housing “d”	Standard
60079-2	Pressure housing “p”	Standard
60079-5	Powder filling “q”	Standard
60079-6	Immersion in oil “o”	Standard
60079-7	Increased safety “e”	Standard
60079-10-1	Gas zone classification	Standard
60079-10-2	fabric zone classification	Standard
60079-11	Intrinsic safety “i”	Standard
60079-12	Sampling devices	Standard
60079-13	Pressure rooms and ventilated rooms	Standard
60079-14	Design, selection and installation	Standard
60079-15	Protection type “n”	Standard
60079-16	HV ventilated housing	Standard
60079-17	Inspection & maintenance	Standard
60079-18	Encapsulation “m”	Standard
60079-19	Repair, overhaul & claims	Standard
80079-20-1	Material data gas	Standard
80079-20-2	Material data fabric	Standard
60079-25	Intrinsically safe systems	Standard
60079-26	EPL Ga Equipment	Standard
60079-27	Capacitive inflammation risks	TS
60079-28	Optical radiation	Standard
60079-29-1	Gas detectors – Performance requirements	Standard
60079-29-2	Gas Detectors – Installation & Maintenance	Standard
60079-29-3	Gas Detectors – Calibration	TR
60079-29-4	Open- path gas detection	Standard
60079-30-1	Electric trace heating – General requirements	Standard
60079-30-2	Electric trace heating – Installation	Standard
60079-31	Dust ignition caused by housing “t”	Standard
60079-32-1	Electrostatic risks – Guidelines	TS
60079-32-2	Electrostatic risks – Test methods	TS
60079-33	Special protection “s”	Standard
60079-35-1	Cap lamps – General requirements	Standard
60079-35-2	Caplamps – Performance	Standard
60079-39	Electronically controlled spark duration limitation	TS
60079-40	Process sealing	TS
60079-42	Devices for controlling ignition sources	TS
60079-43	Ceramic materials	TR
60079-44	Electrical equipment design requirements	TR